

Self-Made Algebraic Magic, Semi-Magic and Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 9

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The work is also available as pdf file at author's sites:

<http://bit.ly/47bnATN>

<http://bit.ly/45RdsNt>

This work is without use of any kind of programming language

Abstract

This work brings *self-made algebraic magic, semi-magic and pandiagonal magic squares*. By *self-made* or *reduced* or *less entries*, we understand that instead of normal n^2 entries of a magic square order n , we are using less numbers, where the magic square is complete in itself. This is just put any integer values of the less entries, one will get always a magic square. Moreover, in these situations the entries are no more sequential numbers. These *entries* are *non-sequential positive and negative* numbers. In some cases, these entries may be *decimal* or *fractional* values depending on the way of choosing the entries. Sometimes to avoid *decimal* or *fractional* we apply certain conditions. These conditions depends on the types of magic squares. The name *self-made* is not known in the literature of magic squares. It is being introduced for first time here in this work. The work is based on different types of magic squares, i.e., *pandiagonal, block-wise, cornered, single-digit bordered, double-digit bordered, etc.* It is not necessary, but we worked with *magic rectangles with equal width and length* for the same category within a magic square. If we relax this condition, i.e., by considering only equality of width, still we have good results. For more details refer author's work [30]. Previously, the author brought similar kind of work [30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35] for the orders 3 to 12 specially for the for the *dates* and *days* of the year 2025, where the *dates* are few *entries* and *days* are the *sums* of magic squares. Total there are 46 magic squares, out of them 10 are just magic squares, 9 are *semi-magic* later these 9 are converted to magic squares and 18 are *pandiagonal* magic squares.

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Contents

1	Introduction	3
2	Magic Squares of Order 9	4
3	Self-Made Algebraic Magic Squares of Order 9	6
3.1	With Magic Square of Order 3	6
3.2	With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5	17
3.3	With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 7	23
4	Self-Made Semi-Magic Squares of Order 9	26
4.1	With Magic Square of Order 3	26
4.2	With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5	43
4.3	With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 7	49
5	Self-Made Algebraic Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 9	53
6	Author’s Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers	88

1 Introduction

This work brings **self-made algebraic magic**, **semi-magic** and **pandiagonal** magic squares . By **self-made** or **reduced** or **less entries**, we understand that instead of normal n^2 entries of a magic square order n , we are using less numbers, where the magic square is complete in itself. This just put any integer values of the less entries, one will get always a magic square. Moreover, in these situations the entries are no more sequential numbers. These **entries** are **non-sequential positive** and **negative** numbers. In some cases, these may be **decimal** or **fractional** values depending on the way of choosing the entries. Sometimes to avoid **decimal** or **fractional** we apply certain conditions. These conditions depends on the types of magic squares. The name **self-made** is not known in the literature of magic squares. It is being introduced for first time here in this work. The work is based on different types of magic squares, i.e., **pandiagonal**, **block-wise**, **cornered**, **single-digit bordered**, **double-digit bordered**, etc. It is not necessary, but we worked with **magic rectangles** with **equal width** and **length** for the same category within a magic square. If we relax this condition, i.e., by considering only equality of width, still we have good results. For more details refer author's work [30]. Previously, the author brought similar kind of work [30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35] for the orders 3 to 12 specially for the for the **dates** and **days** of the year 2025, where the **dates** are few **entries** and **days** are the **sums** of magic squares. Total there are 46 magic squares, out of them 10 are just magic squares, 9 are **semi-magic** later converted to magic squares and 18 are **pandiagonal** magic squares. The work on **magic**, **semi-magic** and **magic from semi-magic** are rewritten from author's previous work [36]. See below the table:

Magic Squares	10
Semi-Magic Squares	9
Magic From Semi-Magic Squares	9
Pandiagonal Magic Squares	18
Total	46

The author [30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35] also worked on similar kind of work but from different point of view. This work is for the magic squares of orders 3 to 12 for the **dates** and **days** of the year 2025, where the **dates** are few entries and **days** are the sums of the magic squares. For general work refer the recent work of author [36, 37, 38, 39, 40].

2 Magic Squares of Order 9

Example 2.1. Let's consider following 4 magic squares of order 9

9x9	pan	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	9x9	mgc						369			
369	22	71	30	27	64	32	20	69	34	369		69	16	80	12	72	17	21	56	26	369
369	35	21	67	28	23	72	33	25	65	369		13	66	2	70	10	65	61	58	24	369
369	66	31	26	68	36	19	70	29	24	369		73	9	38	34	51	32	50	6	76	369
369	40	8	75	45	1	77	38	6	79	369		68	14	44	48	31	39	43	79	3	369
369	80	39	4	73	41	9	78	43	2	369		11	71	46	36	41	52	30	7	75	369
369	3	76	44	5	81	37	7	74	42	369		78	4	42	40	53	33	37	59	23	369
369	58	53	12	63	46	14	56	51	16	369		19	63	35	47	29	49	45	22	60	369
369	17	57	49	10	59	54	15	61	47	369		20	62	55	25	77	8	67	1	54	369
	48	13	62	50	18	55	52	11	60	369		18	64	27	57	5	74	15	81	28	369
1	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	2	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

9x9	mgc									369	9x9	mgc									369
	38	43	42	50	32	27	55	15	67	369		8	80	78	76	75	12	14	16	10	369
	45	41	37	46	36	62	20	8	74	369		1	58	54	56	21	20	18	60	81	369
	40	39	44	49	33	26	56	80	2	369		3	17	50	53	33	35	34	65	79	369
	34	35	52	31	53	65	17	10	72	369		5	19	30	40	45	38	52	63	77	369
	48	47	30	29	51	23	59	14	68	369		73	59	31	39	41	43	51	23	9	369
	60	54	57	18	58	21	19	77	5	369		71	57	46	44	37	42	36	25	11	369
	22	28	25	64	24	63	61	81	1	369		69	55	48	29	49	47	32	27	13	369
	78	75	16	13	79	76	12	11	9	369		67	22	28	26	61	62	64	24	15	369
	4	7	66	69	3	6	70	73	71	369		72	2	4	6	7	70	68	66	74	369
3	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	4	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

The first magic square is **pandiagonal** magic square, where the blocks of order 3 are equal sums **semi-magic** squares. The second magic square is **double-digit bordered** magic square embedded with magic square of order 5. It has four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×5 . The third magic square is **cornered** magic squares, where the magic squares of orders 3, 5 and 7 are at upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×3 , 2×5 and 2×7 are of equal width and length for each order. The forth magic square is **single-digit bordered** magic square. It includes magic squares of orders 3, 5 and 7.

More details on these types of magic squares given in Example 3.1 refer author's work [11, 16, 24, 27]. Based on above four examples given in 3.1, we shall construct the **self-made algebraic** magic squares of order 9. There are three types as given below

- (i) Normal magic squares;
- (ii) Semi-Magic Squares, and Converted in Magic Squares;
- (iii) Pandiagonal Magic Squares

3 Self-Made Algebraic Magic Squares of Order 9

It is again divided in three parts. Having magic squares of order 3. The other two parts are with pandiagonal magic squares of orders 5 and 7.

3.1 With Magic Square of Order 3

Result 3.1. *Let's consider following self-made algebraic magic square of order 9:*

$(S-L)/2+A28+2*A12+A17-A18$	A28	$3*(S-L)/4+A19+A20+A21+A22$	$(L-S)/2-A19$	$(L-S)/2-A20$	$(L-S)/2-A21$	$(L-S)/2-A22$	$(5*S-L)/4-A28-A12-A17$	$(L-S)/2-A28-A12+A18$
$(9*S-5*L)/4+A17-A23+A12$	$L-S-A28-2*A12-A17+A18$	$5*(L-S)/4-A19-A20-A21-A22$	A19	A20	A21	A22	A28+A12-A18	A23
$3*(S-L)/4+A24+A25+A26+A27$	$5*(L-S)/4-A24-A25-A26-A27$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(S-M)/2-A5-A6$	$A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	$5*(L-S)/4-A13-A14-A15-A16$	$3*(S-L)/4+A13+A14+A15+A16$
$(L-S)/2-A24$	A24	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	A5	S-M-A5	A13	$(L-S)/2-A13$
$(L-S)/2-A25$	A25	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A6	S-M-A6	A14	$(L-S)/2-A14$
$(L-S)/2-A26$	A26	$A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A4	$A1+2*(S-M)-2*A4+A2-2*A5-A6$	$(S-M)/2$	$2*M-S$	A15	$(L-S)/2-A15$
$(L-S)/2-A27$	A27	$A1+3*(S-M)/2+A2-2*A5-A6-A4$	S-M-A4	$2*A4-S+M-A1-A2+2*A5+A6$	$2*M-S$	$(S-M)/2$	A16	$(L-S)/2-A16$
$L-S-A28-2*A12+A18-2*A17+A23$	A12	$5*(L-S)/4-A8-A9-A10-A11$	A8	a21	A10	A11	A17	$(9*S-5*L)/4+A28+A12-A18+A17-A23$
$(L-S)/2-A12$	$(9*S-5*L)/4+A12+A17-A18$	$3*(S-L)/4+A8+A9+A10+A11$	$(L-S)/2-A8$	$(L-S)/2-A9$	$(L-S)/2-A10$	$(L-S)/2-A11$	A18	$(L-S)/2-A17$

• Details

It is double-digit bordered magic square of order 9 embedded with cornered magic square of order 5 containing magic square of order 3 at upper-left corner. The four magic rectangles of order 2×5 are of equal sums, i.e.,

equal width and equal length. To avoid decimal entries we must have magic sum of magic square of order 3 as a multiple of 3. The letters M, S and L are magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5 and 9 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 3.1. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 3.1:

1a	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								200	1b	mgc	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT								221
	41	38	62	11	10	9	8	13	8	200		31	38	47	21	20	19	18	9	18	221
	36	-1	-22	29	30	31	32	32	33	200		12	19	3	29	30	31	32	32	33	221
	82	-42	3	28	29	59	1	2	38	200		67	-17	2	30	31	56	2	27	23	221
	6	34	46	20	-6	15	45	23	17	200		16	34	50	21	-8	15	43	23	27	221
	5	35	11	12	37	16	44	24	16	200		15	35	11	12	40	16	42	24	26	221
	4	36	7	14	69	30	0	25	15	200		14	36	8	14	65	29	5	25	25	221
	3	37	53	46	-9	0	30	26	14	200		13	37	50	44	-7	5	29	26	24	221
	5	22	22	18	19	20	21	27	46	200		25	22	47	18	19	20	21	27	22	221
	18	41	18	22	21	20	19	28	13	200		28	17	3	32	31	30	29	28	23	221
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200		221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221

The magic sums are given by

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 60$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 120$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 200$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 63$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 121$$

$$L_{7 \times 7} = 221$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 60 \times 90$$

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 40 \times 100$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 58 \times 87$$

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 50 \times 125$$

Result 3.2. Let's consider following *self-made algebraic magic square* of order 9:

$(T-M)/2-A12$	A14	$A10+A11-(T-M)/4$	$(T-M)/2-A10$	$(T-M)/2-A11$	A9	$(5*M-T)/4+A12-A14-A9$	A23	L-T-A23
A13	A12	$3*(T-M)/4-A10-A11$	A10	A11	$(3*T-7*M)/4-A12+A14+A9$	$(5*M-T)/2-A13-A14-A9$	A24	L-T-A24
$A15+A16-(T-M)/4$	$3*(T-M)/4-A15-A16$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(T-M)/4-A7-A8$	$A7+A8-(T-M)/4$	A25	L-T-A25
$(T-M)/2-A15$	A15	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	A7	$(T-M)/2-A7$	A26	L-T-A26
$(T-M)/2-A16$	A16	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A8	$(T-M)/2-A8$	$7*(L-T)/2-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27-A28$	$5*(T-L)/2+A23+A24+A25+A26+A27+A28$
$A14-A6+A9$	$(3*T-7*M)/4-A12+A13+A14-A6+A9$	$3*(T-M)/4-A4-A5$	A4	A5	$(5*M-T)/2+A12-2*A14-2*A9-A13+A6$	A6	A27	L-T-A27
$(5*M-T)/4+A12-A13-A14+A6-A9$	$(5*M-T)/2-2*A14+A6-A9-A13$	$A4+A5-(T-M)/4$	$(T-M)/2-A4$	$(T-M)/2-A5$	$A14+A13-A6$	$T-3*M-A12+2*A14+2*A9+A13-A6$	A28	L-T-A28
A18	$(5*T-3*M)/2-L+A18-2*A4-A5+A1+A2-2*A7-A8-A24+A23$	A19	A20	$(9*L+3*M)/2-6*T-2*A18+2*A4+A5-A1-A2+2*A7+A8+A24-A23-A19-A20-A21-A22$	A21	A22	$(L-T)/2$	$4*T-3*L$
L-T-A18	$2*L+(3*M-7*T)/2-A18+2*A4+A5-A1-A2+2*A7+A8+A24-A23$	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	$5*T-(7*L+3*M)/2+2*A18-2*A4-A5+A1+A2-2*A7-A8-A24+A23+A19+A20+A21+A22$	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	$4*T-3*L$	$(L-T)/2$

• Details

It is *cornered* magic square of order 9 with *double-digit bordered* magic square of order 7 at upper-left having a magic square of order 3 in the middle of it. The four magic rectangles of order 2×3 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length. Also, the magic rectangles of order 2×7 are of equal sums. To avoid decimal entries we must have magic sum of magic square of order 3 as a multiple of 3. The letters M, T and L are the magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 7 and 9 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 3.2. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 3.2:

2a	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								200	2b	mgc	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT								201
	-13	47	65	-9	-11	37	4	65	15	200		-11	47	64	-7	-9	37	0	65	15	201
	45	43	-35	39	41	26	-39	67	13	200		45	43	-32	39	41	32	-47	67	13	201
	85	-55	24	17	19	-23	53	69	11	200		84	-52	25	15	17	-20	52	69	11	201
	-19	49	15	20	25	33	-3	71	9	200		-17	49	11	19	27	33	-1	71	9	201
	-21	51	21	23	16	35	-5	-140	220	200		-19	51	21	23	13	35	-3	-140	220	201
	53	40	-11	27	29	-49	31	73	7	200		53	46	-8	27	29	-57	31	73	7	201
	-10	-55	41	3	1	61	79	75	5	200		-14	-63	40	5	3	61	89	75	5	201
	55	-77	57	59	62	61	63	40	-120	200		55	-71	57	59	56	61	63	40	-119	201
	25	157	23	21	18	19	17	-120	40	200		25	151	23	21	24	19	17	-119	40	201
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200		201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201

The magic sums are given by

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 60$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 120$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 200$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 57$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 121$$

$$L_{7 \times 7} = 201$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 30 \times 45$$

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 80 \times 280$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 32 \times 48$$

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 80 \times 280$$

Result 3.3. Let's consider following *self-made algebraic magic square* of order 9:

$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(S-M)/2-A5-A6$	$A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A11	T-S-A11	A21	L-T-A21
$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	A5	S-M-A5	A12	T-S-A12	A22	L-T-A22
A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A6	S-M-A6	A13	T-S-A13	A23	L-T-A23
$A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A4	$A1+2*(S-M)-2*A4+A2-2*A5-A6$	(S-M)/2	$2*M-S$	$5*(T-S)/2-A11-A12-A13-A14$	$3*(S-T)/2+A11+A12+A13+A14$	A24	L-T-A24
$A1+3*(S-M)/2+A2-2*A5-A6-A4$	S-M-A4	$2*A4-S+M-A1-A2+2*A5+A6$	$2*M-S$	(S-M)/2	A14	T-S-A14	$7*(L-T)/2-A21-A22-A23-A24-A25-A26$	$5*(T-L)/2+A21+A22+A23+A24+A25+A26$
$T-3*S/2-M/2+A8+2*A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A12-A11$	A8	A9	$3*T/2-S+M/2-2*A8-2*A4+A1+A2-2*A5-A12+A11-A9-A10$	A10	(T-S)/2	$3*S-2*T$	A25	L-T-A25
$S/2+M/2-A8-2*A4+A1+A2-2*A5-A12+A11$	T-S-A8	T-S-A9	$2*A8+2*A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A12-A11+A9+A10-T/2-M/2$	T-S-A10	$3*S-2*T$	(T-S)/2	A26	L-T-A26
A16	$5*S-4*T-L+A16+2*A13+2*A4+2*A1+2*A21-A22-A1-A2+2*A9+2*A8+2*A5+A10+A14$	A17	A18	$(9*L+T)/2-5*S-2*A16-2*A13-2*A4-2*A12-A21+A22+A1+A2-2*A9-2*A8-2*A5-A10-A14-A17-A18-A19-A20$	A19	A20	(L-T)/2	$4*T-3*L$
L-T-A16	$2*L+3*T-5*S-A16-2*A13-2*A4-2*A12-A21+A22+A1+A2-2*A9-2*A8-2*A5-A10-A14$	L-T-A17	L-T-A18	$5*S-(3*T+7*L)/2+2*A16+2*A13+2*A4+2*A12+A21-A22-A1-A2+2*A9+2*A8+2*A5+A10+A14+A17+A18+A19+A20$	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	$4*T-3*L$	(L-T)/2

• Details

It is *cornered* magic square of order 9 with *cornered* magic square of order 7 at upper-left corner having a magic square of order 5 and 3 again at upper-left corner. Each two magic rectangles of orders 2×3 , 2×5 and 2×7 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length in each case. Again, to avoid decimal entries we must have magic sum of magic square of order 3 as a multiple of 3. The letters M, S, T and L are the magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 3.3. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 3.3:

3a	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								240
	3	28	29	44	6	21	39	31	39	240
	46	20	-6	15	35	22	38	32	38	240
	11	12	37	16	34	23	37	33	37	240
	12	14	49	25	10	60	0	34	36	240
	38	36	1	10	25	24	36	44	26	240
	29	18	19	64	20	30	-10	35	35	240
	31	42	41	-4	40	-10	30	36	34	240
	26	-102	27	28	207	29	30	35	-40	240
	44	172	43	42	-137	41	40	-40	35	240
	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240

3b	mgc	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT								241
	2	30	31	41	7	21	39	31	39	241
	50	21	-8	15	33	22	38	32	38	241
	11	12	40	16	32	23	37	33	37	241
	13	14	45	24	15	60	0	34	36	241
	35	34	3	15	24	24	36	44	26	241
	27	18	19	66	20	30	-9	35	35	241
	33	42	41	-6	40	-9	30	36	34	241
	26	-102	27	28	207	29	30	35	-39	241
	44	172	43	42	-137	41	40	-39	35	241
	241	241	241	241	241	241	241	241	241	241

The magic sums are given by

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 60$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 110$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 170$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 240$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 63$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 111$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 171$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 241$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 50 \times 75$$

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 60 \times 150$$

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 70 \times 245$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 48 \times 72$$

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 60 \times 150$$

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 70 \times 245$$

Result 3.4. Let's consider following *self-made algebraic magic square* of order 9:

A6	$2*M-A9-S+A7$	S-M-A7	S-M-A6	A9	A14	T-S-A14	$2*L-5*T-A24-A7+2*S+2*A15+2*A11+2*A12+A17$	$4*T-L+A24+A7-2*S-2*A15-2*A11-2*A12-A17$
$2*S-3*M+A9-2*A7+A2+A1-A4$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$2*M-S+A4+2*A7-A2-A1-A9$	A15	T-S-A15	L-T-A24	A24
$2*A7+S-M-A6-A2-A1$	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	$A6-2*A7+A2+A1$	$(5/2)*T-(5/2)*S-A17-A16-A15-A14$	$(3/2)*S-(3/2)*T+A14+A15+A16+A17$	L-T-A25	A25
A4	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	S-M-A4	A16	T-S-A16	L-T-A26	A26
$4*M-2*S-A9$	$A9+2*S-3*M-A7$	A7	A6	S-M-A6	A17	T-S-A17	$(13*T-7*L)/2+A26+A25+2*A24+A28+A27+A7-2*S-2*A15-2*A11-2*A12-A17$	$(9*L-15*T)/2-A26-A25-2*A24-A28-A27-A7+2*S+2*A15+2*A11+2*A12+A17$
$T-2*S-A7+A11+M+A6+A15-A14$	A11	$A7-(1/2)*S-M-A6+(3/2)*T-A13-A12-2*A11-A15+A14$	A12	A13	(T-S)/2	$3*S-2*T$	L-T-A27	A27
$A7-A11+S-M-A6-A15+A14$	T-S-A11	$A13+A12+2*A11-A7+M+A6+A15-A14-(1/2)*T-(1/2)*S$	T-S-A12	T-S-A13	$3*S-2*T$	(T-S)/2	L-T-A28	A28
A19	$A19-2*A16-A13$	$(7/2)*L-(7/2)*T-A22-A21-A20-A23+2*A16+A13-2*A19$	A20	A21	A22	A23	(L-T)/2	$4*T-3*L$
L-T-A19	$L-T+2*A16+A13-A19$	$(5/2)*T-(5/2)*L+A22+A21+A20+A23-2*A16-A13+2*A19$	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	$4*T-3*L$	(L-T)/2

● Details

It is *cornered* magic square of order 9 with *cornered* magic square of order 7 at upper-left corner having a *single-digit bordered* magic square of order 5 at upper-left corner. It has magic square of order 3 in the middle. Each two magic rectangles of orders 2×5 and 2×7 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length in each case. Again, to avoid decimal entries we must have magic sum of magic square of order 3 as a multiple of 3. The magic sum of magic square of order 5 may be *semi-magic* but still we have order 9 as a magic square. The letters M, S, T and L are the magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 3.4. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 3.3:

4a	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								200
16	58	13	14	19	24	6	2	48	200	
-36	-7	48	49	66	25	5	16	34	200	
25	86	30	-26	5	-27	57	15	35	200	
14	11	12	67	16	26	4	14	36	200	
101	-28	17	16	14	27	3	103	-53	200	
21	21	-12	22	23	15	60	13	37	200	
9	9	42	8	7	60	15	12	38	200	
29	-46	66	30	31	32	33	25	0	200	
21	96	-16	20	19	18	17	0	25	200	
200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	

4b	mgc	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT								261
16	57	14	15	19	24	6	121	-11	261	
-34	-7	48	49	65	25	5	76	34	261	
26	86	30	-26	5	-27	57	75	35	261	
14	11	12	67	17	26	4	74	36	261	
99	-26	17	16	15	27	3	-106	216	261	
20	21	-11	22	23	15	61	73	37	261	
10	9	41	8	7	61	15	72	38	261	
29	-46	276	30	31	32	33	55	-179	261	
81	156	-166	80	79	78	77	-179	55	261	
261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261	

The magic sums are given by

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 90$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 120$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 150$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 200$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 90$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 121$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 151$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 261$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 30 \times 75$$

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 50 \times 175$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 30 \times 75$$

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 110 \times 385$$

Result 3.5. Let's consider following *self-made algebraic magic square* of order 9:

A15	$(7/2)*T-(9/2)*S-A8+A5-2*M-A11$	A8	$(9/2)*S-A15-A16-A10-A9-A5+2*M-(5/2)*T+A11$	A9	A10	A16	A23	L-T-A23
$(5/2)*T-(5/2)*S-A15+A16-A14+2*A8-A5+2*M-A13-A11$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(S-M)/2-A5-A6$	$A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	$(3/2)*S-(3/2)*T+A11-2*A8+A5-2*M+A13+A14-A16+A15$	A24	L-T-A24
$A5-(7/2)*S-2*M+(5/2)*T-2*A8$	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	A5	S-M-A5	$(5/2)*S-(3/2)*T+2*A8-A5+2*M$	A25	L-T-A25
A13	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A6	S-M-A6	T-S-A13	A26	L-T-A26
A14	$A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A4	$A1+2*(S-M)-2*A4+A2-2*A5-A6$	$(S-M)/2$	$2*M-S$	T-S-A14	$7*(L-T)/2-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27-A28$	$5*(T-L)/2+A23+A24+A25+A26+A27+A28$
A11	$A1+3*(S-M)/2+A2-2*A5-A6-A4$	S-M-A4	$2*A4-S+M-A1-A2+2*A5+A6$	$2*M-S$	$(S-M)/2$	T-S-A11	A27	L-T-A27
$6*S-A16-4*T$	$A11+A8-A5+(7/2)*S+2*M-(5/2)*T$	T-S-A8	$A15+A16+A10+A9+(7/2)*T-(11/2)*S+A5-2*M-A11$	T-S-A9	T-S-A10	T-S-A15	A28	L-T-A28
A18	$(5*T-3*M)/2-L+A18-2*A4-A5+A1+A2-2*S-A8-A24+A23$	A19	A20	$(9*L+3*M)/2-6*T-2*A18+2*A4+A5-A1-A2+2*S+A8+A24-A23-A19-A20-A21-A22$	A21	A22	$(L-T)/2$	$4*T-3*L$
L-T-A18	$2*L+(3*M-7*T)/2-A18+2*A4+A5-A1-A2+2*S+A8+A24-A23$	L-T-A19	#VALOR!	$5*T-(7*L+3*M)/2+2*A18-2*A4-A5+A1+A2-2*S-A8-A24+A23+A19+A20+A21+A22$	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	$4*T-3*L$	$(L-T)/2$

● Details

It is *cornered* magic square of order 9 with *single-digit bordered* magic square of order 7 at upper-left corner embedded with a *cornered* magic square of order 5. It has magic square of order 3 at the upper-left corner of it. The two magic rectangles of orders 2×7 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length. Again, to avoid decimal entries we must have magic sum of magic square of order 3 as a multiple of 3. The magic sum of magic square of order 7 may be *semi-magic* but still we have order 9 as a magic square. The letters M, S, T and L are the magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 3.5. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 3.5:

5a	pan	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								200
25	-246	18	288	19	20	26	33	17	200	
194	-7	48	49	23	13	-170	34	16	200	
-267	86	30	-26	15	21	291	35	15	200	
23	11	12	67	16	20	1	36	14	200	
24	19	14	21	18	54	0	-38	88	200	
21	17	22	15	54	18	3	37	13	200	
130	270	6	-264	5	4	-1	38	12	200	
28	-223	29	30	248	31	32	25	0	200	
22	273	21	20	-198	19	18	0	25	200	
200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	

5b	pan	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT								211
25	-160	18	227	19	20	26	33	3	211	
265	-8	50	51	17	15	-215	34	2	211	
-207	90	31	-28	15	17	257	35	1	211	
23	11	12	70	16	16	27	36	0	211	
24	21	14	13	16	61	26	-87	123	211	
21	11	18	19	61	16	29	37	-1	211	
24	210	32	-177	31	30	25	38	-2	211	
28	-174	29	30	150	31	32	18	67	211	
8	210	7	6	-114	5	4	67	18	211	
211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211	211	

The magic sums are given by

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 90$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 126$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 150$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 200$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 93$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 125$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 175$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 211$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 36 \times 54$$

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 50 \times 175$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 32 \times 48$$

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 36 \times 126$$

Result 3.6. Let's consider following *self-made algebraic magic square* of order 9:

A18	$T-S+A11+A15-A14$	A11	$S-A18-A19-A13-A12-2*A11-A15+A14$	A12	A13	A19	$L-S-A21+A22-A11+A7-A2-A5-A15+A27-A1$	$S-T+A21-A22+A11-A7+A2+A5+A15-A27+A1$
$5*T-6*S-A18+A19-A17-A15-A16-A14$	A6	$M-A6-A9-A8+A7$	$S-M-A7$	A8	A9	$5*S-4*T+A14+A15+A16+A17-A19+A18$	A27	$L-T-A27$
A15	$3*S-4*M-A6+A9-A5-A4$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*M-2*S+A4+A5-A9+A6$	T-S-A15	A28	$L-T-A28$
A16	A5	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	$S-M-A5$	T-S-A16	A29	$L-T-A29$
A17	A4	A1	A2	$M-A1-A2$	$S-M-A4$	T-S-A17	$(5*L-7*T)/2+ A21-A22+S+A11-A7+A2+A5+A15-2*A27+A1-A28-A29-A30-A31$	$(5*T-3*L)/2-A21+A22-S-A11+A7-A2-A5-A15+2*A27-A1+A28+A29+A30+A31$
A14	$4*M-2*S-A9$	$A6+A9+A8+S-2*M-A7$	A7	$S-M-A8$	$S-M-A6$	T-S-A14	A30	$L-T-A30$
$6*S-A19-4*T$	$A14-A11-A15$	T-S-A11	$A18+A19+A13+A12+2*A11+T-2*S+A15-A14$	T-S-A12	T-S-A13	T-S-A18	A31	$L-T-A31$
A21	A22	A23	A24	$7*(L-T)/2-A21-A22-A23-A24-A25-A26$	A25	A26	$(L-T)/2$	$4*T-3*L$
$L-T-A21$	$L-T-A22$	$L-T-A23$	$L-T-A24$	$5*(T-L)/2+A21+A22+A23+A24+A25+A26$	$L-T-A25$	$L-T-A26$	$4*T-3*L$	$(L-T)/2$

• Details

It is *cornered* magic square of order 9 with *single-digit bordered* magic square of order 7 at upper-left corner embedded with a *cornered* magic square of orders 5 and 3. The two magic rectangles of orders 2×7 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length. Again, to avoid decimal entries we must have magic sum of magic square of order 3 as a multiple of 3. The magic sum of magic square of order 7 may be *semi-magic* but still we have order 9 as a magic square. The letters M, S, T and L are the magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 3.6. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 3.6:

6a	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								230	6b	mgc	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT								321
	79	95	51	-242	55	59	83	73	-23	230		79	106	51	-232	55	59	83	154	-34	321
	-212	31	12	15	39	43	252	115	-65	230		-167	31	12	25	39	43	218	115	5	321
	67	22	-4	45	49	28	-27	119	-69	230		67	52	-4	45	49	8	-16	119	1	321
	71	27	83	30	-23	23	-31	123	-73	230		71	27	83	30	-23	33	-20	123	-3	321
	75	23	11	15	64	27	-35	-513	563	230		75	23	11	15	64	37	-24	-349	469	321
	63	37	38	35	11	19	-23	127	-77	230		63	17	48	35	21	29	-12	127	-7	321
	37	-55	-11	282	-15	-19	-39	131	-81	230		13	-55	0	283	-4	-8	-28	131	-11	321
	91	95	99	103	-431	107	111	25	30	230		91	95	99	103	-186	107	111	60	-159	321
	-41	-45	-49	-53	481	-57	-61	30	25	230		29	25	21	17	306	13	9	-159	60	321
	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230		321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321

The magic sums are given by

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 90$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 140$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 180$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 230$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 90$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 150$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 201$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 321$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 50 \times 175$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 120 \times 420$$

3.2 With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

Result 3.7. Let's consider following *self-made algebraic magic square* of order 9:

$(S-L)/2+A30+2*A14+A19-A20$	A30	$3*(S-L)/4+A21+A22+A23+A24$	$(L-S)/2-A21$	$(L-S)/2-A22$	$(L-S)/2-A23$	$(L-S)/2-A24$	$(5*S-L)/4-A30-A14-A19$	$(L-S)/2-A30-A14+A20$
$(9*S-5*L)/4+A19-A25+A14$	$L-S-A30-2*A14-A19+A20$	$5*(L-S)/4-A21-A22-A23-A24$	A21	A22	A23	A24	A30+A14-A20	A25
$3*(S-L)/4+A26+A27+A28+A29$	$5*(L-S)/4-A26-A27-A28-A29$	A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4	$5*(L-S)/4-A15-A16-A17-A18$	$3*(S-L)/4+A15+A16+A17+A18$
$(L-S)/2-A26$	A26	A8-A2+A7	A5	A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7	A6	S-A1-A3-A4-A8	A15	$(L-S)/2-A15$
$(L-S)/2-A27$	A27	A2+A3+A4-A5-A7	S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8	A7	A7-A2-A3+A5+A8	A1+A2+A3-A6-A7	A16	$(L-S)/2-A16$
$(L-S)/2-A28$	A28	A7-A3+A5	A1-A6+A8	A2+A3-A7	S-A1-A5-A7-A8	A7-A2+A6	A17	$(L-S)/2-A17$
$(L-S)/2-A29$	A29	S-A1-A4-A7-A8	A3+A4-A5	A7-A2-A3+A5+A6	A1+A2-A6	A8	A18	$(L-S)/2-A18$
$L-S-A30-2*A14+A20-2*A19+A25$	A14	$5*(L-S)/4-A10-A11-A12-A13$	A10	A11	A12	A13	A19	$(9*S-5*L)/4+A30+A14-A20+A19-A25$
$(L-S)/2-A14$	$(9*S-5*L)/4+A14+A19-A20$	$3*(S-L)/4+A10+A11+A12+A13$	$(L-S)/2-A10$	$(L-S)/2-A11$	$(L-S)/2-A12$	$(L-S)/2-A13$	A20	$(L-S)/2-A19$

• Details

It is *double-digit bordered* magic square of order 9 with embedded with *pandiagonal* magic square of order 5 at the middle of it. The four magic rectangles of orders 2×5 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length. The letters S and L are the magic sums of magic squares of orders 5 and 9 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 3.7. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 3.7:

7a	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								200	7b	mgc	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT								231
	101	69	156	-11	-13	-15	-17	-53	-17	200		87	69	135	3	1	-1	-3	-57	-3	231
	45	-61	-116	51	53	55	57	57	59	200		13	-33	-81	51	53	55	57	57	59	231
	196	-156	11	13	64	15	17	-68	108	200		175	-121	11	13	67	15	17	-33	87	231
	-21	61	35	19	-7	21	52	39	1	200		-7	61	35	19	-7	21	55	39	15	231
	-23	63	3	60	23	39	-5	41	-1	200		-9	63	3	63	23	39	-5	41	13	231
	-25	65	27	15	5	42	31	43	-3	200		-11	65	27	15	5	45	31	43	11	231
	-27	67	44	13	35	3	25	45	-5	200		-13	67	47	13	35	3	25	45	9	231
	-49	37	-28	29	31	33	35	47	65	200		-21	37	7	29	31	33	35	47	33	231
	3	55	68	11	9	7	5	49	-7	200		17	23	47	25	23	21	19	49	7	231
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200		231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231

The magic sums are given by

First Example

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 120$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 200$$

Second Example

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 123$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 231.$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 40 \times 100$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 54 \times 135.$$

Result 3.8. *Let's consider following self-made algebraic magic square of order 9:*

A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4	A13	T-S-A13	$2*L-5*T-A23-A7+2*S+2*A14+2*A10+2*A11+A16$	$4*T-L+A23+A7-2*S-2*A14-2*A10-2*A11-A16$
A8-A2+A7	A5	A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7	A6	S-A1-A3-A4-A8	A14	T-S-A14	L-T-A23	A23
A2+A3+A4-A5-A7	S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8	A7	A7-A2-A3+A5+A8	A1+A2+A3-A6-A7	$5*(T-S)/2-A16-A15-A14-A13$	$3*(S-T)/2+A13+A14+A15+A16$	L-T-A24	A24
A7-A3+A5	A1-A6+A8	A2+A3-A7	S-A1-A5-A7-A8	A7-A2+A6	A15	T-S-A15	L-T-A25	A25
S-A1-A4-A7-A8	A3+A4-A5	A7-A2-A3+A5+A6	A1+A2-A6	A8	A16	T-S-A16	$(13*T-7*L)/2+A25+A24+2*A23+A27+A26+A7-2*S-2*A14-2*A10-2*A11-A16$	$(9*L-15*T)/2-A25-A24-2*A23-A27-A26-A7+2*S+2*A14+2*A10+2*A11+A16$
T-S-A7+A10-A8+A14-A13	A10	$A7+A8+3*(T-S)/2-A12-A11-2*A10-A14+A13$	A11	A12	$(T-S)/2$	$3*S-2*T$	L-T-A26	A26
A7-A10+A8-A14+A13	T-S-A10	$(S-T)/2+A12+A11+2*A10-A7-A8+A14-A13$	T-S-A11	T-S-A12	$3*S-2*T$	$(T-S)/2$	L-T-A27	A27
A18	A18-2*A15-A12	$7*(L-T)/2-A21-A20-A19-A22+2*A15+A12-2*A18$	A19	A20	A21	A22	$(L-T)/2$	$4*T-3*L$
L-T-A18	L-T+2*A15+A12-A18	$5*(T-L)/2+A21+A20+A19+A22-2*A15-A12+2*A18$	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	$4*T-3*L$	$(L-T)/2$

Example 3.8. *Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 3.8:*

8a	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								220	8b	mgc	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT								231
	11	14	48	17	20	47	-7	118	-48	220		11	14	49	17	20	47	-7	137	-57	231
	47	23	-16	26	30	50	-10	-7	77	220		47	23	-16	26	31	50	-10	3	77	231
	-1	42	29	53	-13	-106	146	-10	80	220		-1	43	29	53	-13	-106	146	0	80	231
	35	17	2	15	41	53	-13	-13	83	220		35	17	2	16	41	53	-13	-3	83	231
	18	14	47	-1	32	56	-16	192	-122	220		19	14	47	-1	32	56	-16	158	-78	231
	20	38	-43	41	44	20	30	-16	86	220		20	38	-43	41	44	20	31	-6	86	231
	20	2	83	-1	-4	30	20	-19	89	220		20	2	83	-1	-4	31	20	-9	89	231
	62	-88	-7	65	68	71	74	35	-60	220		62	-88	28	65	68	71	74	40	-89	231
	8	158	77	5	2	-1	-4	-60	35	220		18	168	52	15	12	9	6	-89	40	231
	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220		231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231

The magic sums are given by

First Example

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 110$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 150$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 220$$

Second Example

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 111$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 151$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 231$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 40 \times 100$$

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 70 \times 245$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 40 \times 100$$

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 80 \times 280$$

● **Details**

It is **cornered** magic square of order 9 with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 at upper-left corner. It contains magic square of order 7 also as a **cornered** magic square. The magic rectangles of orders 2×5 and 2×7 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length in each case. The letters S, T and L are the magic sums of magic squares of orders 5, 7 and 9 respectively. See below two examples.

Result 3.9. Let's consider following *self-made algebraic magic square* of order 9:

A17	$T-S+A_{10}+A_{14}-A_{13}$	A10	$S-A_{17}-A_{18}-A_{12}-A_{11}-2*A_{10}-A_{14}+A_{13}$	A11	A12	A18	L-T-A25	A25
A14	A1	A2	$S-A_1-A_2-A_3-A_4$	A3	A4	T-S-A14	L-T-A26	A26
$5*T-6*S-A_{17}+A_{18}-A_{16}-A_{14}-A_{15}-A_{13}$	$A_8-A_2+A_7$	A5	$A_1+A_2+A_3+A_4-A_5-A_6-A_7$	A6	$S-A_1-A_3-A_4-A_8$	$5*S-4*T+A_{13}+A_{14}+A_{15}+A_{16}-A_{18}+A_{17}$	$5*(T-L)/2+A_{26}+A_{25}+A_{27}+A_{28}+A_{29}+A_{30}$	$7*(L-T)/2-A_{26}-A_{25}-A_{27}-A_{28}-A_{29}-A_{30}$
A15	$A_2+A_3+A_4-A_5-A_7$	$S-A_1-A_2-A_3-A_4+A_6-A_8$	A7	$A_7-A_2-A_3+A_5+A_8$	$A_1+A_2+A_3-A_6-A_7$	T-S-A15	L-T-A27	A27
A16	$A_7-A_3+A_5$	$A_1-A_6+A_8$	$A_2+A_3-A_7$	$S-A_1-A_5-A_7-A_8$	$A_7-A_2+A_6$	T-S-A16	L-T-A28	A28
A13	$S-A_1-A_4-A_7-A_8$	$A_3+A_4-A_5$	$A_7-A_2-A_3+A_5+A_6$	$A_1+A_2-A_6$	A8	T-S-A13	L-T-A29	A29
$6*S-A_{18}-4*T$	$A_{13}-A_{10}-A_{14}$	T-S-A10	$A_{17}+A_{18}+A_{12}+A_{11}+2*A_{10}+T-2*S+A_{14}-A_{13}$	T-S-A11	T-S-A12	T-S-A17	L-T-A30	A30
A20	$5*T-A_{25}+A_{26}-A_{13}+A_{18}+A_8-5*S+A_7-A_{14}+A_{10}+A_{20}-A_{16}-A_{15}-A_{17}-L$	$(9*L-17*T)/2-A_{23}-A_{22}-A_{21}-A_{24}+A_{25}-A_{26}+A_{13}-A_{18}-A_8+5*S-A_7+A_{14}-A_{10}-2*A_{20}+A_{16}+A_{15}+A_{17}$	A21	A22	A23	A24	(L-T)/2	$4*T-3*L$
L-T-A20	$2*L-6*T+A_{25}-A_{26}+A_{13}-A_{18}-A_8+5*S-A_7+A_{14}-A_{10}-A_{20}+A_{16}+A_{15}+A_{17}$	$(15*T-7*L)/2+A_{23}+A_{22}+A_{21}+A_{24}-A_{25}+A_{26}-A_{13}+A_{18}+A_8-5*S+A_7-A_{14}+A_{10}+2*A_{20}-A_{16}-A_{15}-A_{17}$	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	L-T-A24	$4*T-3*L$	(L-T)/2

• Details

It is *cornered* magic square of order 9 with *single-digit bordered* magic square of order 7 at upper-left corner. It contains *pandiagonal* magic square of order 5 in the middle. The magic rectangles of order 2×7 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length. The magic sum of magic square of order 7 may be *semi-magic* but still we have order 9 as a magic square. The letters S, T and L are the magic sums of magic squares of orders 5, 7 and 9 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 3.9. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 3.9:

9a	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								220	9b	mgc	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT								251
	63	115	42	-199	45	48	66	-47	87	220		63	116	42	-199	45	48	66	-17	87	251
	54	15	18	32	21	24	16	-50	90	220		54	15	18	32	21	24	17	-20	90	251
	21	51	27	-12	30	14	49	467	-427	220		26	51	27	-12	30	14	45	392	-322	251
	57	3	26	33	57	-9	13	-53	93	220		57	3	26	33	57	-9	14	-23	93	251
	60	39	21	6	-1	45	10	-56	96	220		60	39	21	6	-1	45	11	-26	96	251
	51	2	18	51	3	36	19	-59	99	220		51	2	18	51	3	36	20	-29	99	251
	-126	-45	28	269	25	22	7	-62	102	220		-130	-45	29	270	26	23	8	-32	102	251
	72	97	-347	75	78	81	84	20	60	220		72	71	-216	75	78	81	84	35	-29	251
	-32	-57	387	-35	-38	-41	-44	60	20	220		-2	-1	286	-5	-8	-11	-14	-29	35	251
	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220		251	251	251	251	251	251	251	251	251	251

The magic sums are given by

First Example

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 110$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 180$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 220$$

Second Example

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 110$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 181$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 251$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 40 \times 140$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 70 \times 245$$

3.3 With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 7

Result 3.10. *Let's consider following self-made algebraic magic square of order 9:*

$A7+A22+A9+A10+A14+A1+A2+A6+A3+A5-A12-T-A16$	$A8+A23+A19-A1-A15-A6-A17+A12+A13+A4-A5$	A1	A6	$A22-A10+A19+A2-A18-A13+A3$	A15	$2^*T-A8+A16-A7-2^*A22-A9-A23-2^*A19-A14-A1-2^*A2+A18-A6+A17-2^*A3-A4$	A30	L-T-A30
$A19+A14+A2-A18-A17+A12+A3+2^*A4-A5-A7$	$T+A16-A7-A22-A19+A20-A14-A1-2^*A2-A11+A18-A6+A17-A3$	A2	A7	A11	$A7+A22-A19-A20+A1+A6-A12-2^*A4+A5-A16$	A19	A31	L-T-A31
$T-A9-A10+A23-A14-A1-A15-A6+A12-A3-A5$	$2^*A7+2^*A22+A9+A19-A20+A14+2^*A1+2^*A2+A11-A18+A15+2^*A6-A12-A13+2^*A3-A4+2^*A5-2^*T-A16$	$A14+A11+A15+A6-A4-A23-A20$	$2^*T-A8-A7-A22-A9-A23-2^*A19-A14-2^*A2-A11+A18-A6+A17-A12-A3-A4$	$A8-A7-A22+A9+A10+A23+A19+A20-A1-A11-A15-A6-A17+A12+A13+3^*A4-A5$	A16	A20	A32	L-T-A32
$T-A22-A23-A19-A20-A21-A2+A18+A15-A12-A4$	$A10-A23-A19+A1+A6-A12+A5$	$T+A23+A20-A14-A1-A2-A11-A15-A6-A3-A5$	$A22-A10+A23+2^*A19+A14+2^*A2+A11-A18-A17+A12+A3+A4-T$	A12	A17	A21	A33	L-T-A33
$T-A7-A22+A23+A20-A14-A1-A2-A11-A15-2^*A6+A12+A13-A3+A4-A5$	$A16-A7-A22+A23+A19+A20+A21-A1-A15-A6+2^*A12+A13-A3+2^*A4-A5$	A3	A8	$T-A8+A7-A9-A23-2^*A19-A20-A14+A1-A2+A18+A15+A6+A17-2^*A12-A13-A3-3^*A4+A5$	$A7+A22+A9-A23+A19-A20-A21+2^*A14+A1+2^*A2+A11-A18+A15+2^*A6-A17-A12-A13+2^*A3+A5-T-A16$	A22	A34	L-T-A34
$A7+A22-A23-A20+A14+A1+A2+A11+A15+2^*A6-A12-A13+A3-2^*A4+2^*A5-T$	$A7+A22-A23-A20-A21+A14+A1+A2+A15+A6-A12-A13+A3-A4-A16$	A4	A9	A13	$2^*T+A16-2^*A7-2^*A22-A9+A23+2^*A20+A21-2^*A14-2^*A1-2^*A2-A11-2^*A15-3^*A6+2^*A12+A13-2^*A3+2^*A4-2^*A5$	A23	A35	L-T-A35
$A16+A20+A21-A14-A2+A17-A3$	$2^*T-A8-A7-A22-A9-A10-A19-A14-A1-A2-A6-A3-A4-A5$	A5	A10	A14	A18	$A8-A16+A7+A22+A9+A19-A20-A21+A14+A1+2^*A2-A18+A6-A17+2^*A3+A4-T$	$7^*(L-T)/2-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35$	$5^*(T-L)/2+A30+A31+A32+A33+A34+A35$
A25	$T+A25-A1-2^*A5+A13+A3+3^*A4-A6+2^*A12+A2-A18-A15+2^*A19+A14-A7+A23-2^*A17+A8-A31-L+A30$	A26	A27	A28	A29	$9^*(L-T)/2-A26-A27-A28-A29-2^*A25+2^*A5-A13-A3-3^*A4+A6-2^*A12-A2+A18+A15-2^*A19-A14+A1+A7-A23+2^*A17-A8+A31-A30$	$(L-T)/2$	4^*T-3^*L
L-T-A25	$2^*L-2^*T-A25+A1+2^*A5-A13-A3-3^*A4+A6-2^*A12-A2+A18+A15-2^*A19-A14+A7-A23+2^*A17-A8+A31-A30$	L-T-A26	L-T-A27	L-T-A28	L-T-A29	$7^*(T-L)/2+A26+A27+A28+A29+2^*A25-2^*A5+A13+A3+3^*A4-A6+2^*A12+A2-A18-A15+2^*A19+A14-A1-A7+A23-2^*A17+A8-A31+A30$	4^*T-3^*L	$(L-T)/2$

• Details

It is **cornered** magic square of order 9 with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 7 at upper-left corner. The two magic rectangles of orders 2×7 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length. The letters T and L are the magic sums of magic squares of orders 7 and 9 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 3.10. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 9 based on the Result 3.10:

10a	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								250
	-69	45	11	16	15	25	157	40	10	250
	41	124	12	17	21	-44	29	41	9	250
	112	-193	9	144	72	26	30	42	8	250
	50	-22	126	-34	22	27	31	43	7	250
	120	115	13	18	23	-121	32	44	6	250
	-119	-29	14	19	23	259	33	45	5	250
	65	160	15	20	24	28	-112	-80	130	250
	35	70	36	37	38	39	-80	25	50	250
	15	-20	14	13	12	11	130	50	25	250
	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250

10b	mgc	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT								271
	-80	45	11	16	15	25	179	40	20	271
	41	135	12	17	21	-44	29	41	19	271
	123	-215	9	166	72	26	30	42	18	271
	61	-22	137	-45	22	27	31	43	17	271
	131	115	13	18	34	-132	32	44	16	271
	-130	-29	14	19	23	281	33	45	15	271
	65	182	15	20	24	28	-123	-45	105	271
	35	60	36	37	38	39	-35	30	31	271
	25	0	24	23	22	21	95	31	30	271
	271	271	271	271	271	271	271	271	271	271

The magic sums are given by

First Example

$$S_{7 \times 7} = 200$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 250$$

Second Example

$$S_{7 \times 7} = 211$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 271.$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 50 \times 175$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 7} = 60 \times 210.$$

4 Self-Made Semi-Magic Squares of Order 9

Based on the examples 2, 3 and 4 given in 3.1 we shall bring eight different ways to write **self-made semi-magic** squares of order 9. It is divided in two parts. The first is with magic square of order 3. The second part is with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5.

4.1 With Magic Square of Order 3

Result 4.1. *Let's consider following self-made algebraic magic square of order 9:*

$(L-S)/2-A29$	A30	$A21+A22+A23+A24-2*(L-S)$	$(L-S)/2-A21$	$(L-S)/2-A22$	$(L-S)/2-A23$	$(L-S)/2-A24$	$(7*S-3*L)/2-A15-A20-A30$	$A29+2*L-3*S+A15+A20$
A31	A29	$5*(L-S)/2-A21-A22-A23-A24$	A21	A22	A23	A24	$(5*S-3*L)/2-A29-A15-A20$	$A15+A20-A31$
$A25+A26+A27+A28-2*(L-S)$	$5*(L-S)/2-A25-A26-A27-A28$	A6	$M-A6-A9-A8+A7$	$S-M-A7$	A8	A9	$5*(L-S)/2-A16-A17-A18-A19$	$A16+A17+A18+A19-2*(L-S)$
$(L-S)/2-A25$	A25	$3*S-4*M-A6+A9-A5-A4$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*M-2*S+A4+A5-A9+A6$	A16	$(L-S)/2-A16$
$(L-S)/2-A26$	A26	A5	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	$S-M-A5$	A17	$(L-S)/2-A17$
$(L-S)/2-A27$	A27	A4	A1	A2	$M-A1-A2$	$S-M-A4$	A18	$(L-S)/2-A18$
$(L-S)/2-A28$	A28	$4*M-2*S-A9$	$A6+A9+A8+S-2*M-A7$	A7	$S-M-A8$	$S-M-A6$	A19	$(L-S)/2-A19$
$(7*S-3*L)/2-A15-A31-A30$	$(5*S-3*L)/2-A15-A29-A30$	$5*(L-S)/2-A11-A12-A13-A14$	A11	A12	A13	A14	$(3*L-7*S)/2+A29+2*A15+A20+A30$	$A30-A20+A31$
$2*L-3*S+A29+A15+A30$	A15	$A11+A12+A13+A14-2*(L-S)$	$(L-S)/2-A11$	$(L-S)/2-A12$	$(L-S)/2-A13$	$(L-S)/2-A14$	A20	$3*S-L-A29-2*A15-A20-A30$

● **Details**

It is **double-digit bordered semi-magic** square of order 9 embedded with a **single-digit bordered magic** square of order 5. The four magic rectangles of order 2×5 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length. The magic square of order 3 is with decimal entries. To get the result without decimal entries, we must consider magic sum for order 3 as multiple of 3. It is **semi-magic** because of **single-digit bordered magic** square of order 5 in the middle. To get it a magic square of order 9, we must have a condition $M = \frac{3}{5} \times S$. The letters M, S and L are magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5 and 9 respectively.

● **Magic Square Derived From the Result 4.1**

After apply the condition $M = \frac{3}{5} \times S$ over the Result 4.1, the **semi-magic** becomes a magic square given by

$(\frac{5}{6}) * M - (\frac{1}{2}) * L + A31 + 2 * A15 + A20 - A21$	A31	$(\frac{5}{4}) * M - (\frac{3}{4}) * L + A22 + A23 + A24 + A25$	$(\frac{1}{2}) * L - (\frac{5}{6}) * M - A22$	$(\frac{1}{2}) * L - (\frac{5}{6}) * M - A23$	$(\frac{1}{2}) * L - (\frac{5}{6}) * M - A24$	$(\frac{1}{2}) * L - (\frac{5}{6}) * M - A25$	$(\frac{25}{12}) * M - (\frac{1}{4}) * L - A31 - A15 - A20$	$(\frac{1}{2}) * L - (\frac{5}{6}) * M - A31 - A15 + A21$
$(\frac{15}{4}) * M - (\frac{5}{4}) * L + A20 - A26 + A15$	$L - (\frac{5}{3}) * M - A31 - 2 * A15 - A20 + A21$	$(\frac{5}{4}) * L - (\frac{25}{12}) * M - A22 - A23 - A24 - A25$	A22	A23	A24	A25	A31 + A15 - A21	A26
$(\frac{5}{4}) * M - (\frac{3}{4}) * L + A27 + A28 + A29 + A30$	$(\frac{5}{4}) * L - (\frac{25}{12}) * M - A27 - A28 - A29 - A30$	A6	$M - A6 - A9 - A8 + A7$	$(\frac{5}{3}) * M - M - A7$	A8	A9	$(\frac{5}{4}) * L - (\frac{25}{12}) * M - A16 - A17 - A18 - A19$	$(\frac{5}{4}) * M - (\frac{3}{4}) * L + A16 + A17 + A18 + A19$
$(\frac{1}{2}) * L - (\frac{5}{6}) * M - A27$	A27	$M - A6 + A9 - A5 - A4$	$A1 + A2 - M/3$	$2 * M/3 - A2$	$2 * M/3 - A1$	$A4 + A5 - A9 + A6 - (\frac{1}{3}) * M$	A16	$(\frac{1}{2}) * L - (\frac{5}{6}) * M - A16$
$(\frac{1}{2}) * L - (\frac{5}{6}) * M - A28$	A28	A5	$4 * M/3 - 2 * A1 - A2$	M/3	$2 * A1 + A2 - (\frac{2}{3}) * M$	$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A5$	A17	$(\frac{1}{2}) * L - (\frac{5}{6}) * M - A17$
$(\frac{1}{2}) * L - (\frac{5}{6}) * M - A29$	A29	A4	A1	A2	$M - A1 - A2$	$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A4$	A18	$(\frac{1}{2}) * L - (\frac{5}{6}) * M - A18$
$(\frac{1}{2}) * L - (\frac{5}{6}) * M - A30$	A30	$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A9$	$A6 + A9 + A8 - (\frac{1}{3}) * M - A7$	A7	$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A8$	$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A6$	A19	$(\frac{1}{2}) * L - (\frac{5}{6}) * M - A19$
$L - (\frac{5}{3}) * M - A31 - 2 * A15 + A21 - 2 * A20 + A26$	A15	$(\frac{5}{4}) * L - (\frac{25}{12}) * M - A11 - A12 - A13 - A14$	A11	A12	A13	A14	A20	$(\frac{15}{4}) * M - (\frac{5}{4}) * L + A31 + A15 - A21 + A20 - A26$
$(\frac{1}{2}) * L - (\frac{5}{6}) * M - A15$	$(\frac{15}{4}) * M - (\frac{5}{4}) * L + A15 + A20 - A21$	$(\frac{5}{4}) * M - (\frac{3}{4}) * L + A11 + A12 + A13 + A14$	$(\frac{1}{2}) * L - (\frac{5}{6}) * M - A11$	$(\frac{1}{2}) * L - (\frac{5}{6}) * M - A12$	$(\frac{1}{2}) * L - (\frac{5}{6}) * M - A13$	$(\frac{1}{2}) * L - (\frac{5}{6}) * M - A14$	A21	$(\frac{1}{2}) * L - (\frac{5}{6}) * M - A20$

Below are two examples based on the above **semi-magic** and magic squares.

Example 4.1. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 4.1:

1a	semi	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								160	1b	mgc	M/3=S/5								240	
	40	41	59	18	17	16	15	-1	15	220			41	29	38	37	36	35	-31	35	240	
	14	10	-9	32	33	34	35	35	36	220			50	41	32	33	34	35	35	36	240	
	79	-29	16	24	43	18	19	15	35	220			49	21	16	24	23	18	19	65	5	240
	13	37	94	3	28	29	-34	26	24	220			33	37	34	3	28	29	6	26	44	240
	12	38	15	46	20	-6	45	27	23	220			32	38	15	46	20	-6	25	27	43	240
	11	39	14	11	12	37	46	28	22	220			31	39	14	11	12	37	26	28	42	240
	10	40	-19	36	17	42	44	29	21	220			30	40	21	16	17	22	24	29	41	240
	16	25	35	21	22	23	24	30	24	220			56	25	85	21	22	23	24	30	-46	240
	25	19	15	29	28	27	26	31	20	220			45	-51	-15	49	48	47	46	31	40	240
	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220			240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240

The first example is **semi-magic** square and second example is a magic square. The second one is obtained by applying the condition $T = \frac{5}{7} \times S$. The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 60$$

$$S_{Sm_{5 \times 5}} = 120$$

$$L_{Sm_{9 \times 9}} = 220$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 60$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 100$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 240$$

The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 50 \times 125$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 70 \times 175$$

Result 4.2. Let's consider following *self-made algebraic magic square* of order 9:

L-T-A31	$T-L-A23-A22-A21-A20-A19-A18+2*A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24$	A18	A19	A20	A21	A22	A23	L-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24
L-T-A24	$(T-S)/2-A12$	A14	$A10+A11-(T-S)/4$	$(T-S)/2-A10$	$(T-S)/2-A11$	A9	$(5*S-T)/4+A12-A14-A9$	A24
L-T-A25	A13	A12	$3*(T-S)/4-A10-A11$	A10	A11	$(3*T-7*S)/4-A12+A14+A9$	$(5*S-T)/2-A13-A14-A9$	A25
L-T-A26	$A15+A16-(T-S)/4$	$3*(T-S)/4-A15-A16$	$A1+A2-S/3$	$2*S/3-A2$	$2*S/3-A1$	$3*(T-S)/4-A7-A8$	$A7+A8-(T-S)/4$	A26
L-T-A27	$(T-S)/2-A15$	A15	$4*S/3-2*A1-A2$	$S/3$	$2*A1+A2-2*S/3$	A7	$(T-S)/2-A7$	A27
L-T-A28	$(T-S)/2-A16$	A16	A1	A2	$S-A1-A2$	A8	$(T-S)/2-A8$	A28
L-T-A29	$A14-A6+A9$	$(3*T-7*S)/4-A12+A13+A14-A6+A9$	$3*(T-S)/4-A4-A5$	A4	A5	$(5*S-T)/2+A12-2*A14-2*A9-A13+A6$	A6	A29
L-T-A30	$(5*S-T)/4+A12-A13-A14+A6-A9$	$(5*S-T)/2-2*A14+A6-A9-A13$	$A4+A5-(T-S)/4$	$(T-S)/2-A4$	$(T-S)/2-A5$	$A14+A13-A6$	$T-3*S-A12+2*A14+2*A9+A13-A6$	A30
$8*T-7*L+A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24$	$2*L-2*T+A23+A22+A21+A20+A19+A18-2*A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24$	L-T-A18	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	A31

• Details

It is *single-digit bordered semi-magic square* of order 9 embedded with a *double-digit bordered magic square* of order 7. The four magic rectangles of order 2×3 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length. The magic square of order 3 is with decimal entries. To get the result without decimal entries, we must consider magic sum for order 3 as multiple of 3. It is *semi-magic* because of *single-digit bordered magic square* of order 9. To get it a magic square of order 9, we must have a condition $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$. The letters M, T and L are magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 7 and 9 respectively.

• **Magic Square Derived From the Result 4.2**

After apply the condition $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$ over the Result 4.2, the **semi-magic** becomes a magic square given by

$(2/7)*T-A31$	$2*A31+A30+A29$ $+A28+A27+A26$ $+A25+A24-$ $(2/7)*T-A23-A22-$ $A21-A20-A19-A18$	A18	A19	A20	A21	A22	A23	$(9/7)*T-A31-A30-$ $A29-A28-A27-$ $A26-A25-A24$
$(2/7)*T-A24$	$(T-M)/2-A12$	A14	$A10+A11-(T-M)/4$	$(T-M)/2-A10$	$(T-M)/2-A11$	A9	$(5*M-T)/4+A12-$ $A14-A9$	A24
$(2/7)*T-A25$	A13	A12	$3*(T-M)/4-A10-$ $A11$	A10	A11	$(3*T-7*M)/4-$ $A12+A14+A9$	$(5*M-T)/2-A13-$ $A14-A9$	A25
$(2/7)*T-A26$	$A15+A16-(T-M)/4$	$3*(T-M)/4-A15-$ $A16$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(T-M)/4-A7-A8$	$A7+A8-(T-M)/4$	A26
$(2/7)*T-A27$	$(T-M)/2-A15$	A15	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	A7	$(T-M)/2-A7$	A27
$(2/7)*T-A28$	$(T-M)/2-A16$	A16	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A8	$(T-M)/2-A8$	A28
$(2/7)*T-A29$	$A14-A6+A9$	$(3*T-7*M)/4-$ $A12+A13+A14-$ $A6+A9$	$3*(T-M)/4-A4-A5$	A4	A5	$(5*M-T)/2+A12-$ $2*A14-2*A9-$ $A13+A6$	A6	A29
$(2/7)*T-A30$	$(5*M-T)/4+A12-$ $A13-A14+A6-A9$	$(5*M-T)/2-2*A14$ $+A6-A9-A13$	$A4+A5-(T-M)/4$	$(T-M)/2-A4$	$(T-M)/2-A5$	$A14+A13-A6$	$T-3*M-A12+$ $2*A14+2*A9+$ $A13-A6$	A30
$A31+A30+A29+A$ $28+A27+A26+A2$ $5+A24-T$	$(4/7)*T+A23+A2$ $2+A21+A20+A19$ $+A18-2*A31-A30-$ $A29-A28-A27-$ $A26-A25-A24$	$(2/7)*T-A18$	$(2/7)*T-A19$	$(2/7)*T-A20$	$(2/7)*T-A21$	$(2/7)*T-A22$	$(2/7)*T-A23$	A31

Below are two examples based on the above **semi-magic** and magic squares.

Example 4.2. *Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 9 based on the Result 4.2:*

2a	semi	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								420	2b	mgc	T/7=L/9								261
	-101	503	79	83	87	91	95	99	-706	230		-73	475	79	83	87	91	95	99	-675	261
	-73	15	63	63	23	19	43	-26	103	230		-45	15	63	63	23	19	43	-23	103	261
	-77	59	55	7	47	51	96	-115	107	230		-49	59	55	7	47	51	93	-109	107	261
	-81	103	-33	6	25	29	31	39	111	230		-53	103	-33	5	27	31	31	39	111	261
	-85	3	67	43	20	-3	35	35	115	230		-57	3	67	47	21	-5	35	35	115	261
	-89	-1	71	11	15	34	39	31	119	230		-61	-1	71	11	15	37	39	31	119	261
	-93	75	124	55	23	27	-135	31	123	230		-65	75	121	55	23	27	-129	31	123	261
	-97	-54	-147	15	47	43	91	205	127	230		-69	-51	-141	15	47	43	91	199	127	261
	926	-473	-49	-53	-57	-61	-65	-69	131	230		733	-417	-21	-25	-29	-33	-37	-41	131	261
	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230		261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261

The first example is **semi-magic** square and second example is a magic square. The second one is obtained by applying the condition $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$. The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 60$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 200$$

$$L_{Sm_{9 \times 9}} = 230$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 63$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 203$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 261.$$

The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 70 \times 105$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 70 \times 105.$$

Result 4.3. Let's consider following *self-made algebraic magic square* of order 9:

L-T-A29	$T-A21-A20-A19-A18-A17-A16-L+2*A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24+A23+A22$	A16	A17	A18	A19	A20	A21	L-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24-A23-A22
L-T-A22	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(S-M)/2-A5-A6$	$A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A11	T-S-A11	A22
L-T-A23	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	A5	S-M-A5	A12	T-S-A12	A23
L-T-A24	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A6	S-M-A6	A13	T-S-A13	A24
L-T-A25	$A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A4	$A1+2*(S-M)-2*A4+A2-2*A5-A6$	(S-M)/2	$2*M-S$	$5*(T-S)/2-A11-A12-A13-A14$	$3*(S-T)/2+A11+A12+A13+A14$	A25
L-T-A26	$A1+3*(S-M)/2+A2-2*A5-A6-A4$	S-M-A4	$2*A4-S+M-A1-A2+2*A5+A6$	$2*M-S$	(S-M)/2	A14	T-S-A14	A26
L-T-A27	$T-3*S/2-M/2+A8+2*A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A12-A11$	A8	A9	$3*T/2-S+M/2-2*A8-2*A4+A1+A2-2*A5-A12+A11-A9-A10$	A10	(T-S)/2	$3*S-2*T$	A27
L-T-A28	$S/2+M/2-A8-2*A4+A1+A2-2*A5-A12+A11$	T-S-A8	T-S-A9	$2*A8+2*A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A12-A11+A9+A10-T/2-M/2$	T-S-A10	$3*S-2*T$	(T-S)/2	A28
$8*T+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24+A23+A22-7*L$	$2*L-2*T+A21+A20+A19+A18+A17+A16-2*A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24-A23-A22$	L-T-A16	L-T-A17	L-T-A18	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	A29

• Details

It is *single-digit bordered semi-magic square* of order 9 embedded with a *cornered magic square* of order 7. The magic rectangles of order 2×3 , 2×5 and 2×7 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length in each case. The magic square of order 3 is with decimal entries. To get the result without decimal entries, we must consider magic sum for order 3 as multiple of 3. It is *semi-magic* because of *single-digit bordered magic square* of order 9. To get it a magic square of order 9, we must have a condition $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$. The letters M, S, T and L are magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9 respectively.

● **Magic Square Derived From the Result 4.3**

After apply the condition $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$ over the Result 4.3, the **semi-magic** becomes a magic square given by

$(2/7)*T-A29$	$T-A21-A20-A19-A18-A17-A16-(9/7)*T + 2*A29 + A28+A27+A26+A25+A24+ A23+A22$	A16	A17	A18	A19	A20	A21	$(9/7)*T-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24-A23-A22$
$(2/7)*T-A22$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(S-M)/2-A5-A6$	$A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A11	T-S-A11	A22
$(2/7)*T-A23$	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	A5	S-M-A5	A12	T-S-A12	A23
$(2/7)*T-A24$	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A6	S-M-A6	A13	T-S-A13	A24
$(2/7)*T-A25$	$A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A4	$A1+2*(S-M)-2*A4 +A2-2*A5-A6$	(S-M)/2	2*M-S	$5*(T-S)/2-A11-A12-A13-A14$	$3*(S-T)/2+A11+A12+A13+A14$	A25
$(2/7)*T-A26$	$A1+3*(S-M)/2+A2-2*A5-A6-A4$	S-M-A4	$2*A4-S+M-A1-A2+2*A5+A6$	2*M-S	(S-M)/2	A14	T-S-A14	A26
$(2/7)*T-A27$	$T-3*S/2-M/2+A8+2*A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A12-A11$	A8	A9	$3*T/2-S+M/2-2*A8-2*A4+A1+A2-2*A5-A12+A11-A9-A10$	A10	(T-S)/2	3*S-2*T	A27
$(2/7)*T-A28$	$S/2+M/2-A8-2*A4+A1+A2-2*A5-A12+A11$	T-S-A8	T-S-A9	$2*A8+2*A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A12-A11+A9+A10-T/2-M/2$	T-S-A10	3*S-2*T	(T-S)/2	A28
$A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24+A23+A22-T$	$2*(9/7)*T-2*T+A21+A20+A19+A18+A17+ A16-2*A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24-A23-A22$	$(2/7)*T-A16$	$(2/7)*T-A17$	$(2/7)*T-A18$	$(2/7)*T-A19$	$(2/7)*T-A20$	$(2/7)*T-A21$	A29

Below are two examples based on the above **semi-magic** and magic squares.

Example 4.3. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 9 based on the Result 4.3:

3a	semi	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								150	3b	mgc	T/7=L/9								288
	19	98	28	29	30	31	32	33	-70	230		23	94	28	29	30	31	32	33	-12	288
	26	3	28	29	44	6	21	39	34	230		30	3	28	29	44	6	21	93	34	288
	25	46	20	-6	15	35	22	38	35	230		29	46	20	-6	15	35	22	92	35	288
	24	11	12	37	16	34	23	37	36	230		28	11	12	37	16	34	23	91	36	288
	23	12	14	49	25	10	60	0	37	230		27	12	14	49	25	10	195	-81	37	288
	22	38	36	1	10	25	24	36	38	230		26	38	36	1	10	25	24	90	38	288
	21	29	18	19	64	20	30	-10	39	230		25	83	18	19	145	20	57	-118	39	288
	20	31	42	41	-4	40	-10	30	40	230		24	31	96	95	-31	94	-118	57	40	288
	50	-38	32	31	30	29	28	27	41	230		76	-30	36	35	34	33	32	31	41	288
	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230		288	288	288	288	288	288	288	288	288	288

The first example is **semi-magic** square and second example is a magic square. The second one is obtained by applying the condition $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$. The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 60$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 110$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 170$$

$$L_{Sm_{9 \times 9}} = 230$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 60$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 110$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 224$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 288$$

The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 50 \times 75$$

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 60 \times 150$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 50 \times 75$$

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 114 \times 285$$

Result 4.4. Let's consider following *self-made algebraic magic square* of order 9:

L-T-A32	T-A24-A23-A22-A21-A20-A19-L+2*A32+A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25	A19	A20	A21	A22	A23	A24	L-A32-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25
L-T-A25	A6	M-A6-A9-A8+A7	S-M-A7	A8	A9	A14	T-S-A14	A25
L-T-A26	3*S-4*M-A6+A9-2*A7-A8+A2+A1-A4	A1+A2-M/3	2*M/3-A2	2*M/3-A1	3*M-2*S+A4+2*A7+A8-A2-A1-A9+A6	A15	T-S-A15	A26
L-T-A27	2*A7+A8-A2-A1	4*M/3-2*A1-A2	M/3	2*A1+A2-2*M/3	S-M-2*A7-A8+A2+A1	(5/2)*T-(5/2)*S-A17-A16-A15-A14	(3/2)*S-(3/2)*T+A14+A15+A16+A17	A27
L-T-A28	A4	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	S-M-A4	A16	T-S-A16	A28
L-T-A29	4*M-2*S-A9	A6+A9+A8+S-2*M-A7	A7	S-M-A8	S-M-A6	A17	T-S-A17	A29
L-T-A30	T-S-A7+A11-A8+A15-A14	A11	A7+A8+(3/2)*T-A13-A12-2*A11-A15+A14-(3/2)*S	A12	A13	(T-S)/2	3*S-2*T	A30
L-T-A31	A7-A11+A8-A15+A14	T-S-A11	(1/2)*S+A13+A12+2*A11-A7-A8+A15-A14-(1/2)*T	T-S-A12	T-S-A13	3*S-2*T	(T-S)/2	A31
8*T+A32+A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25-7*L	2*L-2*T+A24+A23+A22+A21+A20+A19-2*A32-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	L-T-A24	A32

• Details

It is *single-digit bordered semi-magic square* of order 9 embedded with a *cornered magic square* of order 7. It again contains a *single-digit bordered semi-magic* of order 5 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of order 2×5 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length. The magic square of order 3 is with decimal entries. To get the result without decimal entries, we must consider magic sum for order 3 as multiple of 3. It is *semi-magic* because of *single-digit bordered magic square* of order 9. To get it a magic square of order 9, we must have a condition $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$. The *single-digit bordered* of order 5 is also *semi-magic*, but it don't make any effect on the magic sum of order 9. The letters M, S, T and L are magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9 respectively.

● **Magic Square Derived From the Result 4.4**

After apply the condition $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$ over the Result 4.4, the **semi-magic** becomes a magic square given by

$(\frac{2}{7})^*T-A32$	$2*A32+A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25-(\frac{2}{7})^*T-A24-A23-A22-A21-A20-A19$	A19	A20	A21	A22	A23	A24	$(\frac{9}{7})^*T-A32-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25$
$(\frac{2}{7})^*T-A25$	A6	$M-A6-A9-A8+A7$	$S-M-A7$	A8	A9	A14	$T-S-A14$	A25
$(\frac{2}{7})^*T-A26$	$3*S-4*M-A6+A9-2*A7-A8+A2+A1-A4$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*M-2*S+A4+2*A7+A8-A2-A1-A9+A6$	A15	$T-S-A15$	A26
$(\frac{2}{7})^*T-A27$	$2*A7+A8-A2-A1$	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	$M/3$	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	$S-M-2*A7-A8+A2+A1$	$(\frac{5}{2})^*T-(\frac{5}{2})^*S-A17-A16-A15-A14$	$(\frac{3}{2})^*S-(\frac{3}{2})^*T+A14+A15$	A27
$(\frac{2}{7})^*T-A28$	A4	A1	A2	$M-A1-A2$	$S-M-A4$	A16	$T-S-A16$	A28
$(\frac{2}{7})^*T-A29$	$4*M-2*S-A9$	$A6+A9+A8+S-2*M-A7$	A7	$S-M-A8$	$S-M-A6$	A17	$T-S-A17$	A29
$(\frac{2}{7})^*T-A30$	$T-S-A7+A11-A8+A15-A14$	A11	$A7+A8+(\frac{3}{2})^*T-A13-A12-2*A11-A15+A14-(\frac{3}{2})^*S$	A12	A13	$(T-S)/2$	$3*S-2*T$	A30
$(\frac{2}{7})^*T-A31$	$A7-A11+A8-A15+A14$	$T-S-A11$	$(\frac{1}{2})^*S+A13+A12+2*A11-A7-A8+A15-A14-(\frac{1}{2})^*T$	$T-S-A12$	$T-S-A13$	$3*S-2*T$	$(T-S)/2$	A31
$A32+A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25-T$	$(\frac{4}{7})^*T+A24+A23+A22+A21+A20+A19-2*A32-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25$	$(\frac{2}{7})^*T-A19$	$(\frac{2}{7})^*T-A20$	$(\frac{2}{7})^*T-A21$	$(\frac{2}{7})^*T-A22$	$(\frac{2}{7})^*T-A23$	$(\frac{2}{7})^*T-A24$	A32

Below are two examples based on the above **semi-magic** and magic squares.

Example 4.4. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 9 based on the Result 4.4:

4a	semi	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								420	4b	mgc	S/5=T/7								279
	-2	121	29	30	31	32	33	34	-48	260		20	99	29	30	31	32	33	34	-29	279
	5	16	54	33	18	19	24	56	35	260		27	16	54	34	18	19	24	52	35	279
	4	20	-7	48	49	30	25	55	36	260		26	23	-7	48	49	28	25	51	36	279
	3	29	86	30	-26	21	98	-18	37	260		25	29	86	30	-26	22	88	-12	37	279
	2	14	11	12	67	36	26	54	38	260		24	14	11	12	67	37	26	50	38	279
	1	61	-4	17	32	34	27	53	39	260		23	59	-3	17	33	35	27	49	39	279
	0	67	21	67	22	23	40	-20	40	260		22	63	21	61	22	23	38	-11	40	279
	-1	13	59	13	58	57	-20	40	41	260		21	13	55	15	54	53	-11	38	41	279
	248	-81	11	10	9	8	7	6	42	260		91	-37	33	32	31	30	29	28	42	279
	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260		279	279	279	279	279	279	279	279	279	279

The first example is **semi-magic** square and second example is a magic square. The second one is obtained by applying the condition $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$. The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 90$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 140$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 220$$

$$L_{Sm_{9 \times 9}} = 260$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 90$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 141$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 217$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 279$$

The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 80 \times 200$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 76 \times 190$$

Result 4.5. Let's consider following *self-made algebraic magic square* of order 9:

L-T-A31	$T-A23-A22-A21-A20-A19-A18-L+2*A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24$	A18	A19	A20	A21	A22	A23	L-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24
L-T-A24	A15	$T-S+A8+A12-A11$	A8	$S-A15-A16-A10-A9-2*A8-A12+A11$	A9	A10	A16	A24
L-T-A25	$5*T-6*S-A15+A16-A14-A12-A13-A11$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(S-M)/2-A5-A6$	$A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	$5*S-4*T+A11+A12+A13+A14-A16+A15$	A25
L-T-A26	A12	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	A5	S-M-A5	T-S-A12	A26
L-T-A27	A13	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A6	S-M-A6	T-S-A13	A27
L-T-A28	A14	$A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A4	$A1+2*(S-M)-2*A4+A2-2*A5-A6$	(S-M)/2	2*M-S	T-S-A14	A28
L-T-A29	A11	$A1+3*(S-M)/2+A2-2*A5-A6-A4$	S-M-A4	$2*A4-S+M-A1-A2+2*A5+A6$	2*M-S	(S-M)/2	T-S-A11	A29
L-T-A30	$6*S-A16-4*T$	A11-A8-A12	T-S-A8	$A15+A16+A10+A9+2*A8+T-2*S+A12-A11$	T-S-A9	T-S-A10	T-S-A15	A30
$8*T+A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24-7*L$	$2*L-2*T+A23+A22+A21+A20+A19+A18-2*A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24$	L-T-A18	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	A31

• Details

It is *single-digit bordered semi-magic square* of order 9 embedded with a *cornered magic square* of order 5. The magic rectangles of order 2×3 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length. The magic square of order 3 is with decimal entries. To get the result without decimal entries, we must consider magic sum for order 3 as multiple of 3. It is *semi-magic* because of *single-digit bordered magic squares* of orders 9 and 7. To get it a magic square of order 9, we must have two conditions $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$ and $S = \frac{5}{7} \times T$. The letters M, S, T and L are magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9 respectively.

● **Magic Square Derived From the Result 4.5**

After apply the conditions $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$ and $S = \frac{5}{7} \times T$ over the Result 4.5, the **semi-magic** becomes a magic square given by

$(2/5)*S-A31$	$2*A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24-(2/5)*S-A23-A22-A21-A20-A19-A18$	A18	A19	A20	A21	A22	A23	$(9/5)*S-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24$
$(2/5)*S-A24$	A15	$(2/5)*S+A8+A12-A11$	A8	$S-A15-A16-A10-A9-2*A8-A12+A11$	A9	A10	A16	A24
$(2/5)*S-A25$	$S-A15+A16-A14-A12-A13-A11$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(S-M)/2-A5-A6$	$A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	$A11+A12+A13+A14-A16+A15-(3/5)*S$	A25
$(2/5)*S-A26$	A12	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	A5	S-M-A5	$(2/5)*S-A12$	A26
$(2/5)*S-A27$	A13	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A6	S-M-A6	$(2/5)*S-A13$	A27
$(2/5)*S-A28$	A14	$A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A4	$A1+2*(S-M)-2*A4+A2-2*A5-A6$	$(S-M)/2$	$2*M-S$	$(2/5)*S-A14$	A28
$(2/5)*S-A29$	A11	$A1+3*(S-M)/2+A2-2*A5-A6-A4$	S-M-A4	$2*A4-S+M-A1-A2+2*A5+A6$	$2*M-S$	$(S-M)/2$	$(2/5)*S-A11$	A29
$(2/5)*S-A30$	$(2/5)*S-A16$	A11-A8-A12	$(2/5)*S-A8$	$A15+A16+A10+A9+2*A8-(3/5)*S+A12-A11$	$(2/5)*S-A9$	$(2/5)*S-A10$	$(2/5)*S-A15$	A30
$A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24-(7/5)*S$	$(4/5)*S+A23+A22+A21+A20+A19+A18-2*A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24$	$(2/5)*S-A18$	$(2/5)*S-A19$	$(2/5)*S-A20$	$(2/5)*S-A21$	$(2/5)*S-A22$	$(2/5)*S-A23$	A31

Below are two examples based on the above **semi-magic** and magic squares.

Example 4.5. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 9 based on the Result 4.5:

5a	semi	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								240	5b	mgc									225
	9	108	28	29	30	31	32	33	-100	200		9	108	28	29	30	31	32	33	-75	225
	16	25	49	18	-7	19	20	26	34	200		16	25	69	18	-2	19	20	26	34	225
	15	-59	-7	48	49	14	16	89	35	200		15	36	-8	50	51	17	15	14	35	225
	14	22	86	30	-26	15	15	8	36	200		14	22	90	31	-28	15	17	28	36	225
	13	23	11	12	67	16	14	7	37	200		13	23	11	12	70	16	16	27	37	225
	12	24	22	14	9	15	60	6	38	200		12	24	21	14	13	16	61	26	38	225
	11	21	8	16	21	60	15	9	39	200		11	21	11	18	19	61	16	29	39	225
	10	94	-19	12	37	11	10	5	40	200		10	24	-19	32	52	31	30	25	40	225
	100	-58	22	21	20	19	18	17	41	200		125	-58	22	21	20	19	18	17	41	225
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200		225	225	225	225	225	225	225	225	225	225

The first example is **semi-magic** square and second example is a magic square. The second one is obtained by applying the conditions $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$ and $S = \frac{5}{7} \times T$. The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 90$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 150$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 200$$

$$L_{Sm_{9 \times 9}} = 260$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 93$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 125$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 175$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 225$$

The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 30 \times 45$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} = 32 \times 48$$

Result 4.6. Let's consider following *self-made algebraic magic square* of order 9:

L-T-A28	T-L-A34-A33-A32-A31-A30-A29+2*A28+A27+A26+A25+A24+A23+A22+A21	A29	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	L-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24-A23-A22-A21
L-T-A21	A18	T-S+A11+A15-A14	A11	S-A18-A19-A13-A12-2*A11-A15+A14	A12	A13	A19	A21
L-T-A22	5*T-6*S-A18+A19-A17-A15-A16-A14	A6	M-A6-A9-A8+A7	S-M-A7	A8	A9	5*S-4*T+A14+A15+A16+A17-A19+A18	A22
L-T-A23	A15	3*S-4*M-A6+A9-A5-A4	A1+A2-M/3	2*M/3-A2	2*M/3-A1	3*M-2*S+A4+A5-A9+A6	T-S-A15	A23
L-T-A24	A16	A5	4*M/3-2*A1-A2	M/3	2*A1+A2-2*M/3	S-M-A5	T-S-A16	A24
L-T-A25	A17	A4	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	S-M-A4	T-S-A17	A25
L-T-A26	A14	4*M-2*S-A9	A6+A9+A8+S-2*M-A7	A7	S-M-A8	S-M-A6	T-S-A14	A26
L-T-A27	6*S-A19-4*T	A14-A11-A15	T-S-A11	A18+A19+A13+A12+2*A11+T-2*S+A15-A14	T-S-A12	T-S-A13	T-S-A18	A27
8*T-7*L+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24+A23+A22+A21	2*L-2*T+A34+A33+A32+A31+A30+A29-2*A28-A27-A26-A25-A24-A23-A22-A21	L-T-A29	L-T-A30	L-T-A31	L-T-A32	L-T-A33	L-T-A34	A28

• Details

It is *single-digit bordered semi-magic square* of order 9 embedded with a magic square of order 3. The magic square of order 3 is with decimal entries. To get the result without decimal entries, we must consider magic sum for order 3 as multiple of 3. It is *semi-magic* because of *single-digit bordered* magic squares of orders 9, 7 and 5. To get it a magic square of order 9, we must have three conditions $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$, $S = \frac{5}{7} \times T$ and $M = \frac{3}{5} \times S$. The letters M, S, T and L are magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9 respectively. See below two examples.

● **Magic Square Derived From the Result 4.6**

After apply the conditions $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$, $S = \frac{5}{7} \times T$ and $M = \frac{3}{5} \times S$ over the Result 4.6, the **semi-magic** becomes a magic square given by

$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A28$	$2 * A28 + A27 + A26 + A25 + A24 + A23 + A22 + A21 - (\frac{2}{3}) * M - A34 - A33 - A32 - A31 - A30 - A29$	A29	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	$3 * M - A28 - A27 - A26 - A25 - A24 - A23 - A22 - A21$
$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A21$	A18	$(\frac{2}{3}) * M + A11 + A15 - A14$	A11	$(\frac{5}{3}) * M - A18 - A19 - A13 - A12 - 2 * A11 - A15 + A14$	A12	A13	A19	A21
$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A22$	$(\frac{5}{3}) * M - A18 + A19 - A17 - A15 - A16 - A14$	A6	$M - A6 - A9 - A8 + A7$	$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A7$	A8	A9	$A14 + A15 + A16 + A17 - A19 + A18 - M$	A22
$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A23$	A15	$M - A6 + A9 - A5 - A4$	$A1 + A2 - M/3$	$2 * M/3 - A2$	$2 * M/3 - A1$	$A4 + A5 - A9 + A6 - (\frac{1}{3}) * M$	$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A15$	A23
$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A24$	A16	A5	$4 * M/3 - 2 * A1 - A2$	$M/3$	$2 * A1 + A2 - 2 * M/3$	$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A5$	$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A16$	A24
$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A25$	A17	A4	A1	A2	$M - A1 - A2$	$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A4$	$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A17$	A25
$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A26$	A14	$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A9$	$A6 + A9 + A8 - (\frac{1}{3}) * M - A7$	A7	$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A8$	$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A6$	$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A14$	A26
$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A27$	$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A19$	$A14 - A11 - A15$	$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A11$	$A18 + A19 + A13 + A12 + 2 * A11 - M + A15 - A14$	$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A12$	$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A13$	$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A18$	A27
$A28 + A27 + A26 + A25 + A24 + A23 + A22 + A21 - (\frac{7}{3}) * M$	$(\frac{4}{3}) * M + A34 + A33 + A32 + A31 + A30 + A29 - 2 * A28 - A27 - A26 - A25 - A24 - A23 - A22 - A21$	$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A29$	$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A30$	$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A31$	$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A32$	$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A33$	$(\frac{2}{3}) * M - A34$	A28

Below are two examples based on the above **semi-magic** and magic squares.

Example 4.6. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 9 based on the Result 4.6:

6a	semi	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								450	6b	mgc	M/3=S/5=T/7=L/9								243
	-8	55	49	50	51	52	53	54	-136	220		6	41	49	50	51	52	53	54	-113	243
	-1	38	62	31	-55	32	33	39	41	220		13	38	86	31	-70	32	33	39	41	243
	-2	-141	26	34	33	28	29	171	42	220		12	-6	26	25	27	28	29	60	42	243
	-3	35	44	13	38	39	16	-5	43	220		11	35	35	16	32	33	19	19	43	243
	-4	36	25	56	30	4	35	-6	44	220		10	36	25	44	27	10	29	18	44	243
	-5	37	24	21	22	47	36	-7	45	220		9	37	24	21	22	38	30	17	45	243
	-6	34	31	26	27	32	34	-4	46	220		8	34	25	29	27	26	28	20	46	243
	-7	141	-32	-1	85	-2	-3	-8	47	220		7	15	-32	23	124	22	21	16	47	243
	256	-15	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	48	220		167	13	5	4	3	2	1	0	48	243
	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220		243	243	243	243	243	243	243	243	243	243

The first example is **semi-magic** square and second example is a magic square. The second one is obtained by applying the conditions $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$, $S = \frac{5}{7} \times T$ and $M = \frac{3}{5} \times S$. The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 90$$

$$S_{Sm_{5 \times 5}} = 150$$

$$T_{Sm_{7 \times 7}} = 180$$

$$L_{Sm_{9 \times 9}} = 220$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 81$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 135$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 189$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 243$$

4.2 With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

Result 4.7. Let's consider following *self-made algebraic magic square* of order 9:

L-T-A31	T-A23-A22-A21-A20- A19-A18-L+2*A31 +A30+A29+A28+A27 +A26+A25+A24	A18	A19	A20	A21	A22	A23	L-A31-A30-A29- A28-A27-A26- A25-A24
L-T-A24	A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4	A13	T-S-A13	A24
L-T-A25	A8-A2+A7	A5	A1+A2+A3+A4-A5- A6-A7	A6	S-A1-A3-A4-A8	A14	T-S-A14	A25
L-T-A26	A2+A3+A4-A5-A7	S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6- A8	A7	A7-A2-A3+A5+A8	A1+A2+A3-A6-A7	5*(T-S)/2-A16-A15- A14-A13	3*(S-T)/2+A13+ A14+A15+A16	A26
L-T-A27	A7-A3+A5	A1-A6+A8	A2+A3-A7	S-A1-A5-A7-A8	A7-A2+A6	A15	T-S-A15	A27
L-T-A28	S-A1-A4-A7-A8	A3+A4-A5	A7-A2-A3+A5+A6	A1+A2-A6	A8	A16	T-S-A16	A28
L-T-A29	T-S-A7+A10-A8+A14- A13	A10	A7+A8+3*T/2-A12- A11-2*A10-A14+A13- 3*S/2	A11	A12	(T-S)/2	3*S-2*T	A29
L-T-A30	A7-A10+A8-A14+A13	T-S-A10	S/2+A12+A11+2*A1 0-A7-A8+A14-A13- T/2	T-S-A11	T-S-A12	3*S-2*T	(T-S)/2	A30
8*T+A31+A30+A29 +A28+A27+A26+ A25+A24-7*L	2*L-2*T+A23+A22 +A21+A20+A19+A18- 2*A31-A30-A29-A28- A27-A26-A25-A24	L-T-A18	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	A31

● Details

It is *single-digit bordered semi-magic square* of order 9 embedded with a *cornered magic square* of order 7. It contains *pandiagonal magic square* of order 5 at the upper-left corner. It is *semi-magic* because of *single-digit bordered magic squares* of order 9. To get it a magic square of order 9, we must a condition $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$. The letters S , T and L are magic sums of magic squares of orders 5, 7 and 9 respectively.

● Magic Square Derived From the Result 4.7

After apply the conditions $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$, $S = \frac{5}{7} \times T$ and $M = \frac{3}{5} \times S$ over the Result 4.7, the *semi-magic* becomes a magic square given by

$(2/7)*T-A31$	$2*A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24-(2/7)*T-A23-A22-A21-A20-A19-A18$	A18	A19	A20	A21	A22	A23	$(9/7)*T-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24$
$(2/7)*T-A24$	A1	A2	$S-A1-A2-A3-A4$	A3	A4	A13	$T-S-A13$	A24
$(2/7)*T-A25$	$A8-A2+A7$	A5	$A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7$	A6	$S-A1-A3-A4-A8$	A14	$T-S-A14$	A25
$(2/7)*T-A26$	$A2+A3+A4-A5-A7$	$S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8$	A7	$A7-A2-A3+A5+A8$	$A1+A2+A3-A6-A7$	$5*(T-S)/2-A16-A15-A14-A13$	$3*(S-T)/2+A13+A14+A15+A16$	A26
$(2/7)*T-A27$	$A7-A3+A5$	$A1-A6+A8$	$A2+A3-A7$	$S-A1-A5-A7-A8$	$A7-A2+A6$	A15	$T-S-A15$	A27
$(2/7)*T-A28$	$S-A1-A4-A7-A8$	$A3+A4-A5$	$A7-A2-A3+A5+A6$	$A1+A2-A6$	A8	A16	$T-S-A16$	A28
$(2/7)*T-A29$	$T-S-A7+A10-A8+A14-A13$	A10	$A7+A8+3*T/2-A12-A11-2*A10-A14+A13-3*S/2$	A11	A12	$(T-S)/2$	$3*S-2*T$	A29
$(2/7)*T-A30$	$A7-A10+A8-A14+A13$	$T-S-A10$	$S/2+A12+A11+2*A10-A7-A8+A14-A13-T/2$	$T-S-A11$	$T-S-A12$	$3*S-2*T$	$(T-S)/2$	A30
$A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24-T$	$(4/7)*T+A23+A22+A21+A20+A19+A18-2*A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24$	$(2/7)*T-A18$	$(2/7)*T-A19$	$(2/7)*T-A20$	$(2/7)*T-A21$	$(2/7)*T-A22$	$(2/7)*T-A23$	A31

Below are two examples based on the above **semi-magic** and magic squares.

Example 4.7. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 9 based on the Result 4.7:

7a	semi	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								300	7b	mgc	T/7=L/9								225
	-45	340	56	59	62	65	68	71	-426	250		-45	340	56	59	62	65	68	71	-451	225
	-24	5	8	102	11	14	41	19	74	250		-24	5	8	103	11	14	41	-7	74	225
	-27	41	17	-22	20	84	44	16	77	250		-27	41	17	-22	20	85	44	-10	77	225
	-30	-7	96	23	47	-19	-32	92	80	250		-30	-7	97	23	47	-19	-97	131	80	225
	-33	29	11	-4	69	35	47	13	83	250		-33	29	11	-4	70	35	47	-13	83	225
	-36	72	8	41	-7	26	50	10	86	250		-36	73	8	41	-7	26	50	-16	86	225
	-39	46	32	-1	35	38	30	20	89	250		-39	20	32	-40	35	38	17	73	89	225
	-42	14	28	61	25	22	20	30	92	250		-42	14	2	74	-1	-4	73	17	92	225
	526	-290	-6	-9	-12	-15	-18	-21	95	250		501	-290	-6	-9	-12	-15	-18	-21	95	225
	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250		225	225	225	225	225	225	225	225	225	225

The first example is **semi-magic** square and second example is a magic square. The second one is obtained by applying the condition $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$. The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 140$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 200$$

$$L_{Sm_{9 \times 9}} = 250$$

Second Example

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 141$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} = 175$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 225$$

The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 60 \times 150$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 5} = 34 \times 85$$

Result 4.8. Let's consider following *self-made algebraic magic square* of order 9:

L-T-A33	T-A25-A24-A23-A22-A21-A20-L+2*A33+A32+A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26	A20	A21	A22	A23	A24	A25	L-A33-A32-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26
L-T-A26	A17	T-S+A10+A14-A13	A10	S-A17-A18-A12-A11-2*A10-A14+A13	A11	A12	A18	A26
L-T-A27	A14	A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4	T-S-A14	A27
L-T-A28	5*T-6*S-A17+A18-A16-A14-A15-A13	A8-A2+A7	A5	A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7	A6	S-A1-A3-A4-A8	5*S-4*T+A13+A14+A15+A16-A18+A17	A28
L-T-A29	A15	A2+A3+A4-A5-A7	S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8	A7	A7-A2-A3+A5+A8	A1+A2+A3-A6-A7	T-S-A15	A29
L-T-A30	A16	A7-A3+A5	A1-A6+A8	A2+A3-A7	S-A1-A5-A7-A8	A7-A2+A6	T-S-A16	A30
L-T-A31	A13	S-A1-A4-A7-A8	A3+A4-A5	A7-A2-A3+A5+A6	A1+A2-A6	A8	T-S-A13	A31
L-T-A32	6*S-A18-4*T	A13-A10-A14	T-S-A10	A17+A18+A12+A11+2*A10+T-2*S+A14-A13	T-S-A11	T-S-A12	T-S-A17	A32
8*T+A33+A32+A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26-7*L	2*L-2*T+A25+A24+A23+A22+A21+A20-2*A33-A32-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	L-T-A24	L-T-A25	A33

• Details

It is *single-digit bordered semi-magic square* of order 9 embedded with a *pandiagonal magic square* of order 5. It is *semi-magic* because of *single-digit bordered magic squares* of orders 9 and 7. To get it a *magic square* of order 9, we must two conditions $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$ and $S = \frac{5}{7} \times T$. The letters S, T and L are magic sums of magic squares of orders 5, 7 and 9 respectively.

• Magic Square Derived From the Result 4.8

After apply the conditions $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$ and $S = \frac{5}{7} \times T$ over the Result 4.8, the **semi-magic** becomes a *magic square* given by

$(2/5)*S-A33$	$2*A33+A32+A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26-(2/5)*S-A25-A24-A23-A22-A21-A20$	A20	A21	A22	A23	A24	A25	$(9/5)*S-A33-A32-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26$
$(2/5)*S-A26$	A17	$(2/5)*S+A10+A14-A13$	A10	$S-A17-A18-A12-A11-2*A10-A14+A13$	A11	A12	A18	A26
$(2/5)*S-A27$	A14	A1	A2	$S-A1-A2-A3-A4$	A3	A4	$(2/5)*S-A14$	A27
$(2/5)*S-A28$	$S-A17+A18-A16-A14-A15-A13$	$A8-A2+A7$	A5	$A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7$	A6	$S-A1-A3-A4-A8$	$A13+A14+A15+A16-A18+A17-$	A28
$(2/5)*S-A29$	A15	$A2+A3+A4-A5-A7$	$S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8$	A7	$A7-A2-A3+A5+A8$	$A1+A2+A3-A6-A7$	$(2/5)*S-A15$	A29
$(2/5)*S-A30$	A16	$A7-A3+A5$	$A1-A6+A8$	$A2+A3-A7$	$S-A1-A5-A7-A8$	$A7-A2+A6$	$(2/5)*S-A16$	A30
$(2/5)*S-A31$	A13	$S-A1-A4-A7-A8$	$A3+A4-A5$	$A7-A2-A3+A5+A6$	$A1+A2-A6$	A8	$(2/5)*S-A13$	A31
$(2/5)*S-A32$	$(2/5)*S-A18$	$A13-A10-A14$	$(2/5)*S-A10$	$A17+A18+A12+A11+2*A10-(3/5)*S+A14-A13$	$(2/5)*S-A11$	$(2/5)*S-A12$	$(2/5)*S-A17$	A32
$A33+A32+A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26-(7/5)*S$	$(4/5)*S+A25+A24+A23+A22+A21+A20-2*A33-A32-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26$	$(2/5)*S-A20$	$(2/5)*S-A21$	$(2/5)*S-A22$	$(2/5)*S-A23$	$(2/5)*S-A24$	$(2/5)*S-A25$	A33

Below are two examples based on the above **semi-magic** and magic squares.

Example 4.8. *Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 9 based on the Result 4.9:*

8a	semi	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								300	8b	mgc	S/5=T/7=L/9								315
	-13	134	30	31	32	33	34	35	-106	210		22	25	49	50	51	52	53	54	-41	315
	-6	27	81	20	-19	21	22	28	36	210		29	38	102	31	-30	32	33	39	41	315
	-7	24	11	12	70	13	14	36	37	210		28	34	26	49	43	28	29	36	42	315
	-8	83	23	15	2	16	64	-23	38	210		27	35	59	8	48	49	11	35	43	315
	-9	25	7	68	17	25	3	35	39	210		26	36	25	76	35	-6	45	34	44	315
	-10	26	19	13	8	59	21	34	40	210		25	37	24	21	22	62	46	33	45	315
	-11	23	60	12	23	7	18	37	41	210		24	34	41	21	27	42	44	36	46	315
	-12	-28	-21	40	79	39	38	33	42	210		23	31	-32	39	100	38	37	32	47	315
	286	-104	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	43	210		111	45	21	20	19	18	17	16	48	315
	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210		315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315

The magic sums are given by

First Example

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 120$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} = 180$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 210$$

Second Example

$$S_{7 \times 7} = 175$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} = 245$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 315.$$

4.3 With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 7

Result 4.9. Let's consider following self-made algebraic magic square of order 9:

L-T-A38	T-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-L+2*A38+A37+A36+A35+A34+A33+A32+A31	A25	A26	A27	A28	A29	A30	L-A38-A37-A36-A35-A34-A33-A32-A31
L-T-A31	A7+A22+A9+A10+A14+A1+A2+A6+A3+A5-A12-T-A16	A8+A23+A19-A1-A15-A6-A17+A12+A13+A4-A5	A1	A6	A22-A10+A19+A2-A18-A13+A3	A15	2*T-A8+A16-A7-2*A22-A9-A23-2*A19-A14-A1-2*A2+A18-A6+A17-2*A3-A4	A31
L-T-A32	A19+A14+A2-A18-A17+A12+A3+2*A4-A5-A7	T+A16-A7-A22-A19+A20-A14-A1-2*A2-A11+A18-A6+A17-A3	A2	A7	A11	A7+A22-A19-A20+A1+A6-A12-2*A4+A5-A16	A19	A32
L-T-A33	T-A9-A10+A23-A14-A1-A15-A6+A12-A3-A5	2*A7+2*A22+A9+A19-A20+A14+2*A1+2*A2+A11-A18+A15+2*A6-A12-A13+2*A3-A4+2*A5-2*T-A16	A14+A11+A15+A6-A4-A23-A20	2*T-A8-A7-A22-A9-A23-2*A19-A14-2*A2-A11+A18-A6+A17-A12-A3-A4	A8-A7-A22+A9+A10+A23+A19+A20-A1-A11-A15-A6-A17+A12+A13+3*A4-A5	A16	A20	A33
L-T-A34	T-A22-A23-A19-A20-A21-A2+A18+A15-A12-A4	A10-A23-A19+A1+A6-A12+A5	T+A23+A20-A14-A1-A2-A11-A15-A6-A3-A5	A22-A10+A23+2*A19+A14+2*A2+A11-A18-A17+A12+A3+A4-T	A12	A17	A21	A34
L-T-A35	T-A7-A22+A23+A20-A14-A1-A2-A11-A15-2*A6+A12+A13-A3+A4-A5	A16-A7-A22+A23+A19+A20+A21-A1-A15-A6+2*A12+A13-A3+2*A4-A5	A3	A8	T-A8+A7-A9-A23-2*A19-A20-A14+A1-A2+A18+A15+A6+A17-2*A12-A13-A3-3*A4+A5	A7+A22+A9-A23+A19-A20-A21+2*A14+A1+2*A2+A11-A18+A15+2*A6-A17-A12-A13+2*A3+A5-T-A16	A22	A35
L-T-A36	A7+A22-A23-A20+A14+A1+A2+A11+A15+2*A6-A12-A13+A3-2*A4+2*A5-T	A7+A22-A23-A20-A21+A14+A1+A2+A15+A6-A12-A13+A3-A4-A16	A4	A9	A13	2*T+A16-2*A7-2*A22-A9+A23+2*A20+A21-2*A14-2*A1-2*A2-A11-2*A15-3*A6+2*A12+A13-2*A3+2*A4-2*A5	A23	A36
L-T-A37	A16+A20+A21-A14-A2+A17-A3	2*T-A8-A7-A22-A9-A10-A19-A14-A1-A2-A6-A3-A4-A5	A5	A10	A14	A18	A8-A16+A7+A22+A9+A19-A20-A21+A14+A1+2*A2-A18+A6-A17+2*A3+A4-T	A37
8*T+A38+A37+A36+A35+A34+A33+A32+A31-7*L	2*L-2*T+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25-2*A38-A37-A36-A35-A34-A33-A32-A31	L-T-A25	L-T-A26	L-T-A27	L-T-A28	L-T-A29	L-T-A30	A38

• Details

It is *single-digit bordered semi-magic magic square of order 9 embedded with a pandiagonal magic square of order 7 in the middle*. To get it a magic square of order 9, we must apply a condition $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$. The letters T and L are the magic sums of magic squares of orders 7 and 9 respectively.

• Magic Square Derived From the Result 4.9

After apply the condition $T = \frac{7}{9} \times L$ and $S = \frac{5}{7} \times T$ over the Result 4.9, the **semi-magic** becomes a magic square given by

$(2/7)*T-A38$	$T-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-(9/7)*T+2*A38+A37+A36+A35+A34+A33+A32+A31$	A25	A26	A27	A28	A29	A30	$(9/7)*T-A38-A37-A36-A35-A34-A33-A32-A31$
$(2/7)*T-A31$	$A7+A22+A9+A10+A14+A1+A2+A6+A3+A5-A12-T-A16$	$A8+A23+A19-A1-A15-A6-A17+A12+A13+A4-A5$	A1	A6	$A22-A10+A19+A2-A18-A13+A3$	A15	$2*T-A8+A16-A7-2*A22-A9-A23-2*A19-A14-A1-2*A2+A18-A6+A17-2*A3-A4$	A31
$(2/7)*T-A32$	$A19+A14+A2-A18-A17+A12+A3+2*A4-A5-A7$	$T+A16-A7-A22-A19+A20-A14-A1-2*A2-A11+A18-A6+A17-A3$	A2	A7	A11	$A7+A22-A19-A20+A1+A6-A12-2*A4+A5-A16$	A19	A32
$(2/7)*T-A33$	$T-A9-A10+A23-A14-A1-A15-A6+A12-A3-A5$	$2*A7+2*A22+A9+A19-A20+A14+2*A1+2*A2+A11-A18+A15+2*A6-A12-A13+2*A3-A4+2*A5-2*T-A16$	$A14+A11+A15+A6-A4-A23-A20$	$2*T-A8-A7-A22-A9-A23-2*A19-A14-2*A2-A11+A18-A6+A17-A12-A3-A4$	$A8-A7-A22+A9+A10+A23+A19+A20-A1-A11-A15-A6-A17+A12+A13+3*A4-A5$	A16	A20	A33
$(2/7)*T-A34$	$T-A22-A23-A19-A20-A21-A2+A18+A15-A12-A4$	$A10-A23-A19+A1+A6-A12+A5$	$T+A23+A20-A14-A1-A2-A11-A15-A6-A3-A5$	$A22-A10+A23+2*A19+A14+2*A2+A11-A18-A17+A12+A3+A4-T$	A12	A17	A21	A34
$(2/7)*T-A35$	$T-A7-A22+A23+A20-A14-A1-A2-A11-A15-2*A6+A12+A13-A3+A4-A5$	$A16-A7-A22+A23+A19+A20+A21-A1-A15-A6+2*A12+A13-A3+2*A4-A5$	A3	A8	$T-A8+A7-A9-A23-2*A19-A20-A14+A1-A2+A18+A15+A6+A17-2*A12-A13-A3-3*A4+A5$	$A7+A22+A9-A23+A19-A20-A21+2*A14+A1+2*A2+A11-A18+A15+2*A6-A17-A12-A13+2*A3+A5-T-A16$	A22	A35
$(2/7)*T-A36$	$A7+A22-A23-A20+A14+A1+A2+A11+A15+2*A6-A12-A13+A3-2*A4+2*A5-T$	$A7+A22-A23-A20-A21+A14+A1+A2+A15+A6-A12-A13+A3-A4-A16$	A4	A9	A13	$2*T+A16-2*A7-2*A22-A9+A23+2*A20+A21-2*A14-2*A1-2*A2-A11-2*A15-3*A6+2*A12+A13-2*A3+2*A4-2*A5$	A23	A36
$(2/7)*T-A37$	$A16+A20+A21-A14-A2+A17-A3$	$2*T-A8-A7-A22-A9-A10-A19-A14-A1-A2-A6-A3-A4-A5$	A5	A10	A14	A18	$A8-A16+A7+A22+A9+A19-A20-A21+A14+A1+2*A2-A18+A6-A17+2*A3+A4-T$	A37
$A38+A37+A36+A35+A34+A33+A32+A31-T$	$(4/7)*T+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25-2*A38-A37-A36-A35-A34-A33-A32-A31$	$(2/7)*T-A25$	$(2/7)*T-A26$	$(2/7)*T-A27$	$(2/7)*T-A28$	$(2/7)*T-A29$	$(2/7)*T-A30$	A38

Below are two examples based on the above **semi-magic** and magic squares.

Example 4.9. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 9 based on the Result 4.9:

9a	semi	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								300	9b	mgc	T/7=L/9								270
	2	129	35	36	37	38	39	40	-106	250		12	119	35	36	37	38	39	40	-86	270
	9	-69	45	11	16	15	25	157	41	250		19	-79	45	11	16	15	25	177	41	270
	8	41	124	12	17	21	-44	29	42	250		18	41	134	12	17	21	-44	29	42	270
	7	112	-193	9	144	72	26	30	43	250		17	122	-213	9	164	72	26	30	43	270
	6	50	-22	126	-34	22	27	31	44	250		16	60	-22	136	-44	22	27	31	44	270
	5	120	115	13	18	23	-121	32	45	250		15	130	115	13	18	33	-131	32	45	270
	4	-119	-29	14	19	23	259	33	46	250		14	-129	-29	14	19	23	279	33	46	270
	3	65	160	15	20	24	28	-112	47	250		13	65	180	15	20	24	28	-122	47	270
	206	-79	15	14	13	12	11	10	48	250		146	-59	25	24	23	22	21	20	48	270
	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250		270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270

The magic sums are given by

First Example

$$S_{7 \times 7} = 200$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 250$$

Second Example

$$S_{7 \times 7} = 210$$

$$L_{9 \times 9} = 270.$$

5 Self-Made Algebraic Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 9

Above we have given total 19 self-made algebraic pandiagonal magic squares of order 9. Out of them 10 are directly magic squares. Other 9 are semi-magic, later they are magic squares by applying certain conditions. Based on these 19 magic squares below are 18 self-made algebraic pandiagonal magic squares of order 9. These are based on certain conditions. In each case the conditions are different. These are given as results, and each result is followed by two examples.

Result 5.1. *Let's consider following self-made algebraic pandiagonal magic square of order 9:*

$(8/3)*M-A1-A12-A3-A11-A2+A7-A6-A9-A10$	$A10+A9+A6-A4+A1+A12+A3+A2-A7-(4/3)*M$	$A11+A4-(1/3)*M$	$(5/3)*M-A2-A3-A11-A12$	$2*M/3-A1$	$A1+A2+A3+A11+A12-(4/3)*M$	$(5/3)*M-A8-A5-A4-A7$	$A4-A2+A8+A5+A7-A9-(1/3)*M$	$A9-(1/3)*M+A2$
$A10+A9+2*A11+A6+A4+A1+A12+A3+A2-A7-(8/3)*M$	$M/3$	$(10/3)*M-A1-A12-A3-2*A11-A2+A7-A6-A9-A10-A4$	$A1+2*A2+2*A3+2*A11+2*A12-(8/3)*M$	$M/3$	$(10/3)*M-2*A2-2*A3-2*A11-2*A12-A1$	$A8+A5+A4+A9-(5/3)*M+A2+A7$	$M/3$	$(7/3)*M-A7-A8-A5-A4-A9-A2$
$M-A11-A4$	$2*M-A10-A9-A6+A4-A1-A12-A3-A2+A7$	$A1+A12+A3+A11+A2-A7-2*M+A6+A9+A10$	$2*M-A2-A3-A11-A12-A1$	$A1$	$A2+A3+A11+A12-M$	$M-A9-A2$	$A2-A8-A5-A4-A7+M+A9$	$A8+A5+A4+A7-M$
$A2+A3-M/3$	$2*M/3-A3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$A4+A5-M/3$	$2*M/3-A5$	$2*M/3-A4$	$(A1+A12+A3+A11+A2-A7-M)+A6-M/3$	$2*M/3-A6$	$(5/3)*M-A1-A12-A3-A11-A2+A7$
$4*M/3-2*A2-A3$	$M/3$	$2*A2+A3-2*M/3$	$4*M/3-2*A4-A5$	$M/3$	$2*A4+A5-2*M/3$	$(10/3)*M-2*A1-2*A12-2*A3-2*A11-2*A2+2*A7-A6$	$M/3$	$2*A1+2*A12+2*A3+2*A11+2*A2-2*A7-(8/3)*M+A6$
$A2$	$A3$	$M-A2-A3$	$A4$	$A5$	$M-A4-A5$	$A1+A12+A3+A11+A2-A7-M$	$A6$	$2*M-A1-A12-A3-A11-A2+A7-A6$
$A7+A8-M/3$	$2*M/3-A8$	$2*M/3-A7$	$A9+A10-M/3$	$2*M/3-A10$	$2*M/3-A9$	$A11+A12-M/3$	$2*M/3-A12$	$2*M/3-A11$
$4*M/3-2*A7-A8$	$M/3$	$2*A7+A8-2*M/3$	$4*M/3-2*A9-A10$	$M/3$	$2*A9+A10-2*M/3$	$4*M/3-2*A11-A12$	$M/3$	$2*A11+A12-2*M/3$
$A7$	$A8$	$M-A7-A8$	$A9$	$A10$	$M-A9-A10$	$A11$	$A12$	$M-A11-A12$

● **Details**

It is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 9 with nine equal sums magic squares of order 9. Interestingly, the middle value of all these nine magics squares of order 3 are the same and is $M/3$, where M is the sums of the magic square of order 3. Obviously, in this case, the magic sum of order nine is given as $T_{9 \times 9} = 3 \times M$. As we observe that, this magic sum of order 3, i.e., M should be divisible by three, otherwise, we shall have fractional entries. See below two examples.

Example 5.1. Let's consider following two examples of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 9 based on the Result 5.1:

9x9	pan	144	144	144	144	144	144	144	144	144	9x9	pan	135	135	135	135	135	135	135	135	135
144	11	18	19	12	21	15	16	17	15	144	135	3	22	20	7	19	19	11	18	16	135
144	24	16	8	19	16	13	15	16	17	144	135	32	15	-2	27	15	3	20	15	10	135
144	13	14	21	17	11	20	17	15	16	144	135	10	8	27	11	11	23	14	12	19	135
144	9	19	20	13	17	18	14	16	18	144	135	10	17	18	14	15	16	18	14	13	135
144	27	16	5	21	16	11	20	16	12	144	135	23	15	7	17	15	13	10	15	20	135
144	12	13	23	14	15	19	14	16	18	144	135	12	13	20	14	15	16	17	16	12	135
144	19	14	15	23	12	13	27	10	11	144	135	20	12	13	24	10	11	28	8	9	135
144	12	16	20	6	16	26	0	16	32	144	135	8	15	22	2	15	28	-4	15	34	135
	17	18	13	19	20	9	21	22	5	144		17	18	10	19	20	6	21	22	2	135
©IJT	144	144	144	144	144	144	144	144	144	144	©IJT	135	135	135	135	135	135	135	135	135	135

As written above these two are **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 9, with equal sums magic squares of order 3. The magic sums of magic squares of order 3 are 45 and 48, and of order 9 are 135 and 144 respectively.

Result 5.2. Let's consider following *self-made algebraic pandiagonal magic square* of order 9:

$(2/5)*S-A9$	A16	$(3/5)*S+A11+A12-A15-A13-A1-A9$	$(2/5)*S-A10$	$(2/5)*S-A11$	$(2/5)*S-A12$	$A15+A13+A10+A1+A9-(4/5)*S$	$(2/5)*S-A16$	A9
$(3/5)*S-A9-A16$	A9	$A15+A13+A1+A9-(1/5)*S-A11-A12$	A10	A11	A12	$(6/5)*S-A15-A13-A10-A1-A9$	$(2/5)*S-A9$	$A9+A16-(1/5)*S$
$A15+A13+A14+A6-(3/5)*S$	$S-A13-A14-A6-A15$	A1	A2	$A15+A13-A2+A8+A6-A3-A11$	A3	$A11-A15-A13-A1-A8-A6+S$	$S-A6-A7-A13-A8$	$A6+A7+A13+A8-(3/5)*S$
$(2/5)*S-A13$	A13	$A12-A2-A1+A6-A9+(2/5)*S$	A4	$(8/5)*S+A3-A4+A11-A12-A15-2*A13-A10-A5+A2-A8-2*A6$	A5	$A1+A8+A15-A11+2*A13+A10+A6+A9-A3-S$	A6	$(2/5)*S-A6$
$(2/5)*S-A14$	A14	$A3-A4+A11-A12-A15-2*A13-A10+A2-A1-A8-2*A6+(8/5)*S$	$A15+2*A13+A10+A5-A2+A1+A8+A6+A9-S-A3-A11$	$A12+A13+A10+A6-(3/5)*S$	$(2/5)*S-A3+A4+A12-A2-A1+A6-A9$	$(3/5)*S+A3-A12-A13-A10-A5+A2+A1-A6$	A7	$(2/5)*S-A7$
$(2/5)*S-A6$	A6	$A6+A4+A12-A3+A13+A10-(3/5)*S$	$S-A13-A10-A9-A5$	$A2-A6-A12+A3-A13-A10+(3/5)*S$	$(3/5)*S-A4-A12+A9-A6$	$A12+A13+A10+A5-A2+A6-(3/5)*S$	A13	$(2/5)*S-A13$
$(2/5)*S-A15$	A15	$A8-A11+A15-A12+A13+A9+A1-(2/5)*S$	$A11-A15-A6-A4+A3-A13-A1+S-A8$	$A5-A2+A6+A4+A12-A3+A13+A10-(3/5)*S$	$A1+A2-A5$	$S-A1-A13-A10-A9$	A8	$(2/5)*S-A8$
$A9+A16-(1/5)*S$	$(2/5)*S-A9$	$A8+A7+A6+A13+A1-(4/5)*S$	A12	$(8/5)*S-A14-A11-A7-A6-A12-A13-A10$	$A13+A10-A13$	$(1/5)*S+A11+A14-A1-A8$	A9	$(3/5)*S-A9-A16$
A9	$(2/5)*S-A16$	$(6/5)*S-A1-A13-A7-A8-A6$	$(2/5)*S-A12$	$A11+A7+A6+A12+A13+A10-(6/5)*S+A14$	$(2/5)*S-A10$	$(1/5)*S-A11-A14+A1+A8$	A16	$(2/5)*S-A9$

• Details

It is a *double-digit bordered pandiagonal magic square* of order 9 with 4 equal sums *magic rectangles* of order 2×5 , with inner part as *pandiagonal magic square* of order 5. Moreover, whole the magic square is depending on the sum of the magic square of order 5. In this case $T_{9 \times 9} = \frac{5}{9} \times S$, where S is the magic sum of order 5. Moreover, both the magic squares of orders 5 and 9 are *pandiagonal*. See below two examples.

Example 5.2. Let's consider following two examples of *pandiagonal magic squares* of order 9 based on the Result 5.2:

9x9	pan	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	9x9	pan	117	117	117	117	117	117	117	117	117
126	-7	56	-19	-10	-13	-16	128	-28	35	126	117	-9	56	-22	-12	-15	-18	132	-30	35	117
126	-49	35	47	38	41	44	-100	-7	77	126	117	-52	35	48	38	41	44	-106	-9	78	117
126	134	-106	11	14	86	17	-58	-64	92	126	117	137	-111	11	14	86	17	-63	-69	95	117
126	-19	47	38	20	-172	23	161	26	2	126	117	-21	47	36	20	-180	23	166	26	0	117
126	-22	50	-160	170	113	41	-94	29	-1	126	117	-24	50	-168	175	116	39	-97	29	-3	117
126	2	26	116	-73	-82	-13	122	47	-19	126	117	0	26	119	-78	-85	-16	125	47	-21	117
126	-25	53	65	-61	125	2	-61	32	-4	126	117	-27	53	67	-66	128	2	-66	32	-6	117
126	77	-7	89	44	-163	38	62	35	-49	126	117	78	-9	93	44	-171	38	61	35	-52	117
	35	-28	-61	-16	191	-10	-34	56	-7	126		35	-30	-67	-18	197	-12	-35	56	-9	117
©IJT	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	©IJT	117	117	117	117	117	117	117	117	117	117

In this case, the magic squares of orders 5 and 9 both are **pandiagonal**. The magic sums of orders 5 and 9 for the first example are 70 and 126 respectively, and for the second example are 65 and 117 respectively. In each case the four magic rectangles of orders 2×5 are of equal sums.

Result 5.3. Let's consider following *self-made algebraic pandiagonal magic square* of order 9:

$(2/3)*M-A7$	A12	$(2/3)*M+A6-A1-A2$	$A9+A7-(1/3)*M$	$(2/3)*M-A8$	$(2/3)*M-A4$	$A2+A4-A7+A1+A8-A6-A9$	$(2/3)*M-A12$	A7
M-A7-A12	A7	A1+A2-A6	M-A9-A7	A8	A4	$A9-A2-A4+A7+(2/3)*M-A1-A8+A6$	$(2/3)*M-A7$	$A7+A12-(1/3)*M$
$A10+A1+A8-A6-A2$	$A6-A1+A2+(2/3)*M-A10-A8$	A2	$M/3-A2+A3$	$2*M/3-A3$	A1	$2*M/3-A1$	$A10-A7+A4+A8+A5-A6-A9$	$A9-A10+A7+(2/3)*M-A4-A8-A5+A6$
$(2/3)*M-A9$	A9	M-A2-A3	M/3	$A3+A2-M/3$	M/3	M/3	$A7+(2/3)*M-A2-A4$	$A4-A7+A2$
$(2/3)*M-A10$	A10	A3	$M/3+A2-A3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$4*M/3-A1-A3-A2$	$A1-2*M/3+A3+A2$	$M-A8-A5+A2-A10$	$A10+A8+A5-A2-(1/3)*M$
A4-A7+A2	$A7+(2/3)*M-A2-A4$	M-A1-A2	M/3	$A1+A3-M/3$	A2	$(2/3)*M-A3$	A9	$(2/3)*M-A9$
$A9-A4+A7+(1/3)*M-A1-A8+A6$	$A4-A7+(1/3)*M+A8-A6+A1-A9$	$A1+A2-M/3$	M/3	M-A1-A3	A3	$(2/3)*M-A2$	A6	$(2/3)*M-A6$
$A7+A12-(1/3)*M$	$(2/3)*M-A7$	$A9-A10+A7+(1/3)*M-A4-A8-A5+A6+A2$	A4	A5	M-A9-A7	$A10+A8-A6-A2+(1/3)*M$	A7	M-A7-A12
A7	$(2/3)*M-A12$	$A10+A4-A7+A8+A5+(1/3)*M-A6-A2-A9$	$(2/3)*M-A4$	$(2/3)*M-A5$	$A9+A7-(1/3)*M$	$A6+A2+(1/3)*M-A10-A8$	A12	$(2/3)*M-A7$

• Details

It is a *double-digit bordered pandiagonal magic square* of order 9 with 4 equal sums *magic rectangles* of order 2×5 , with inner part as *cornered pandiagonal magic square* of order 3, with magic square of order 3 at the upper-left corner. The two small magic rectangles of order 2×5 are also of equal sums. Moreover, whole the magic square is depending on the sum of the magic square of order 3. In this case $T_{9 \times 9} = 3 \times M$, where M is the magic sum of order 3. Moreover, both the magic squares of orders 5 and 9 are *pandiagonal*. See below two examples.

Example 5.3. Let's consider following two examples of *pandiagonal magic squares* of order 9 based on the Result 5.3:

9x9	pan	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	9x9	pan	99	99	99	99	99	99	99	99	99
108	7	22	17	24	6	10	3	2	17	108	99	5	22	15	25	4	8	3	0	17	99
108	-3	17	7	0	18	14	21	7	27	108	99	-6	17	7	-3	18	14	19	5	28	99
108	21	3	12	13	11	11	13	15	9	108	99	21	1	12	12	9	11	11	15	7	99
108	5	19	11	12	13	12	12	15	9	108	99	3	19	8	11	14	11	11	13	9	99
108	4	20	13	11	12	12	12	-5	29	108	99	2	20	13	10	10	8	14	-8	30	99
108	9	15	13	12	12	12	11	19	5	108	99	9	13	10	11	13	12	9	19	3	99
108	21	3	11	12	12	13	12	16	8	108	99	20	2	12	11	9	13	10	16	6	99
108	27	7	9	14	15	0	22	17	-3	108	99	28	5	8	14	15	-3	21	17	-6	99
	17	2	15	10	9	24	2	22	7	108		17	0	14	8	7	25	1	22	5	99
©IJT	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	©IJT	99	99	99	99	99	99	99	99	99	99

*In this case, the magic squares of orders 5 and 9 both are **pandiagonal** and of order 3 are magic squares. The magic sums of orders 3, 5 and 9 for the first example are 36, 60 and 108 respectively, and for the second example are 33, 55 and 99 respectively. In each case the four magic rectangles of orders 2×3 and 2×5 are of equal sums.*

Result 5.4. Let's consider following *self-made algebraic pandiagonal magic square* of order 9:

M-A10-A6	A11	(1/3)*M-A8-A10+A5+A7	A8+A10+A6-(2/3)*M	(2/3)*M-A5	(2/3)*M-A6	(2/3)*M-A7	(2/3)*M-A11	A10+A6-(1/3)*M
(4/3)*M-A10-A6-A11	A10+A6-(1/3)*M	(1/3)*M+A8+A10-A5-A7	(4/3)*M-A8-A10-A6	A5	A6	A7	M-A10-A6	A10+A6-(2/3)*M+A11
A8+A9+A10-A2-A7	A7+A2+(2/3)*M-A8-A9-A10	A2	A1-A3+M/3	M/3	M-A1-A2	A3	A9-(1/3)*M+A4+A3-A7	A7-A4+M-A3-A9
(2/3)*M-A8	A8	2*M/3-A2 +A3-A1	2*M/3-A2	A2+A3-M/3	2*M/3-A3	A1-A3+A2	A10	(2/3)*M-A10
(2/3)*M-A9	A9	M/3	M/3+A2-A3	M/3	M/3-A2+A3	M/3	(4/3)*M-A5-A4-A9	A9-(2/3)*M+A5+A4
(2/3)*M-A10	A10	A1	A3	M-A2-A3	A2	2*M/3-A1	A8	(2/3)*M-A8
A2+A7-(1/3)*M	M-A2-A7	2*M/3-A3	M/3+A3-A1	M/3	A2+A1-M/3	2*M/3-A2	A5+(2/3)*M-A3-A8-A10+A7	A3+A8+A10-A7-A5
A10+A6-(2/3)*M+A11	M-A10-A6	A7+(2/3)*M-A4+A2-A3-A9	A6	A4	(4/3)*M-A8-A10-A6	A9+A3+A8+A10-A7-(1/3)*M-A2	A10+A6-(1/3)*M	(4/3)*M-A10-A6-A11
A10+A6-(1/3)*M	(2/3)*M-A11	A3+A9-A7+A4-A2	(2/3)*M-A6	(2/3)*M-A4	A8+A10+A6-(2/3)*M	A7+M+A2-A9-A3-A8-A10	A11	M-A10-A6

• Details

It is a *double-digit bordered pandiagonal magic square* of order 9 with 4 equal sums *magic rectangles* of order 2×5 , with inner part as *single-digit bordered pandiagonal magic square* of order 5, embedded with a magic square of order 3. Moreover, whole the magic square is depending on the sum of the magic square of order 3. In this case, $T_{5 \times 5} = \frac{5}{3} \times M$ and $T_{9 \times 9} = 3 \times M$, where M is the magic sum of order 3. Moreover, both the magic squares of orders 5 and 9 are *pandiagonal*, while the order 3 is just a magic square. See below two examples.

Example 5.4. Let's consider following two examples of *pandiagonal magic squares* of order 9 based on the Result 5.4:

9x9	pan	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	9x9	pan	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81
90	-6	21	4	34	5	4	3	-1	26	90	90	81	-9	21	3	36	3	2	1	-3	27	81
90	-17	26	16	-14	15	16	17	-6	37	90	90	81	-21	27	15	-18	15	16	17	-9	39	81
90	28	-8	12	8	10	7	13	19	1	90	90	81	28	-10	12	7	9	4	13	20	-2	81
90	2	18	10	8	15	7	10	20	0	90	90	81	0	18	8	6	16	5	10	20	-2	81
90	1	19	10	9	10	11	10	-8	28	90	90	81	-1	19	9	8	9	10	9	-12	30	81
90	0	20	11	13	5	12	9	18	2	90	90	81	-2	20	11	13	2	12	7	18	0	81
90	19	1	7	12	10	13	8	1	19	90	90	81	20	-2	5	11	9	14	6	-1	19	81
90	37	-6	3	16	14	-14	31	26	-17	90	90	81	39	-9	1	16	14	-18	32	27	-21	81
	26	-1	17	4	6	34	-11	21	-6	90			27	-3	17	2	4	36	-14	21	-9	81
©IJT	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	©IJT	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81

*In this case, the magic squares of orders 5 and 9 both are **pandiagonal** and of order 3 are magic squares. The magic sums of orders 3, 5 and 9 for the first example are 30, 50 and 90, and for the second example are 27, 45 and 81 respectively.*

Result 5.5. Let's consider following *self-made algebraic pandiagonal magic square* of order 9:

$(-7/6)*M$	A_4	$(10/3)*M+A_2-2*A_4-3*A_3$	$A_4+A_3-(13/6)*M+A_1$	$A_4+2*A_3-(1/6)*M-A_1-A_2$	A_3	$(5/2)*M-A_4-A_3$	$A_3+A_4-A_6-3*M$	$(11/3)*M-A_3-A_4+A_6$
$(11/6)*M-2*A_4-2*A_3$	$(11/6)*M$	$2*A_4+3*A_3-(8/3)*M-A_2$	$(17/6)*M-A_4-A_3-A_1$	$(5/6)*M+A_2-A_4-2*A_3+A_1$	$A_4+A_3-(11/6)*M$	$A_4+A_3-(1/2)*M$	$A_3-A_5+A_4-3*M$	$(11/3)*M-A_3+A_5-A_4$
$A_4+A_3-(3/2)*M-A_2$	$(13/6)*M+A_2-A_4-A_3$	$(10/3)*M$	$(5/3)*M-2*A_4-2*A_3$	$2*A_4+2*A_3-4*M$	$M-A_1-A_2$	$A_1+A_2-(1/3)*M$	$(-2*A_4-4*A_3)$	$2*A_4+4*A_3+(2/3)*M$
$(13/3)*M-A_4-A_3-A_1$	$A_4+A_3+A_1-2*(11/6)*M$	$2*A_4+2*A_3-7*M$	$M/3$	$(23/3)*M-2*A_4-2*A_3$	A_1	$(2/3)*M-A_1$	$4*M-A_3-A_4$	$A_3+A_4-(10/3)*M$
$A_2+A_1-(11/6)*M$	$(5/2)*M-A_2-A_1$	$(14/3)*M-2*A_4-2*A_3$	$2*A_4+2*A_3-M$	$(-8/3)*M$	A_2	$(2/3)*M-A_2$	$A_4+3*A_3+(13/3)*M$	$(-11/3)*M-3*A_3-A_4$
$A_4+(5/2)*M+A_3$	$(5/2)*M-A_4-A_3$	$A_2-A_4-2*A_3+A_1-(2/3)*M$	$(13/6)*M-A_1$	$A_4+2*A_3-(1/2)*M-A_2$	$(-7/6)*M$	$(-5/2)*M$	A_5	$(2/3)*M-A_5$
$A_4+A_3-(11/6)*M$	A_3-3*M	$(4/3)*M-A_2+A_4+2*A_3-A_1$	$A_1-(3/2)*M$	$(7/6)*M+A_2-A_4-2*A_3$	$(13/3)*M-2*A_3-A_4$	$(11/6)*M$	A_6	$(2/3)*M-A_6$
$(13/6)*M-A_3-A_4+A_6$	$(10/3)*M-2*A_4-3*A_3+A_5$	$(9/2)*M$	$A_3+A_4-(1/3)*M$	$A_3+A_4-(9/2)*M$	$2*A_3-A_5-2*M+A_4$	$(-5/6)*M-A_6$	$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$
$A_3+A_4-A_6-(3/2)*M$	$2*A_4+3*A_3-A_5-(8/3)*M$	$(-23/6)*M$	$M-A_3-A_4$	$(31/6)*M-A_3-A_4$	$(8/3)*M-2*A_3+A_5-A_4$	$(3/2)*M+A_6$	$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$

• Details

It is a *cornered pandiagonal magic square* of order 9 with *double-digit borered pandiagonal magic square* of order 7 at the upper-left corner. It is embedde with magic square of order 3. We observe that all the magic squares of order 3, 7 and 9 are based on the magic sum of order 3. In this case, $T_{7 \times 7} = \frac{7}{3} \times M$ and $T_{9 \times 9} = 3 \times M$, where M is the magic sum of order 3. The magic rectangles of orders 2×3 and 2×7 are of equal sums in each case. Moreover, the magic squares of orders 7 and 9 both are *pandiagonal*. See below two examples.

Example 5.5. Let's consider following two examples of *pandiagonal magic squares* of order 9 based on the Result 5.5:

9x9	pan	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	9x9	pan	144	144	144	144	144	144	144	144	144
126	-49	23	52	-38	28	19	63	-115	143	126	144	-56	23	72	-51	27	19	78	-133	165	144
126	-7	77	-24	66	0	-35	21	-111	139	126	144	4	88	-40	83	5	-46	18	-129	161	144
126	-36	64	140	-14	-84	16	12	-122	150	126	144	-45	77	160	-4	-108	22	10	-122	154	144
126	129	-101	-210	14	238	11	17	126	-98	126	144	155	-123	-252	16	284	11	21	150	-118	144
126	-51	79	112	42	-112	15	13	262	-234	126	144	-62	94	140	36	-128	15	17	288	-256	144
126	147	63	-63	80	25	-49	-105	27	1	126	144	162	78	-67	93	22	-56	-120	27	5	144
126	-35	-107	91	-52	3	121	77	31	-3	126	144	-46	-125	99	-61	10	147	88	31	1	144
126	80	64	189	28	-147	-50	-66	14	14	126	144	93	84	216	26	-174	-62	-71	16	16	144
	-52	-36	-161	0	175	78	94	14	14	126		-61	-52	-184	6	206	94	103	16	16	144
©IJT	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	©IJT	144	144	144	144	144	144	144	144	144	144

The magic sum of magic squares of orders 3, 7 and 9 for the first example are 42, 98 and 126, and for the second example are 48, 112 and 144 respectively. Moreover, in each case, the magic rectangles of orders 2×3 and 2×7 are of equal sums.

Result 5.6. Let's consider following *self-made algebraic pandiagonal magic square* of order 9:

$(1/3)*M$	A2	$(2/3)*M-A2$	A1	$(2/3)*M-A1$	M-A10-A8	$A8-(1/3)*M+A10$	$(2/3)*M-A8$	A8
$(2/3)*M-A2$	$(1/3)*M$	A2	$2*A6+2*A3+A7+2*A4+2*A5-A8-2*M-A10$	$(8/3)*M+A8+A10-2*A6-2*A3-A7-2*A4-2*A5$	$3*M+A8+A10-3*A6-2*A3-A7-2*A4-2*A5$	$3*A6+2*A3+A7+2*A4+2*A5-(7/3)*M-A8-A10$	$(5/3)*M-A10+2*A6-2*A8$	$A10-2*A6+2*A8-M$
A2	$(2/3)*M-A2$	$(1/3)*M$	$A8+(10/3)*M+A10-2*A6-2*A3-A7-2*A4-2*A5-A1-A2$	$2*A6+2*A3+A7+2*A4+2*A5+A1+A2-A8-(8/3)*M-A10$	$(-1/3)*M-A1+M$	A1	$(2/3)*M-A9$	A9
$(2/3)*M-A1$	$(8/3)*M+A8+A10-2*A6-2*A3-A7-2*A4-2*A5$	$2*A6+2*A3+A7+2*A4+2*A5+A1+A2-A8-(8/3)*M-A10$	$(1/3)*M$	$4*M-A2-2*(5/3)*M$	A6	$(2/3)*M-A6$	$3*A6+2*A3+A7+2*A4+2*A5-(7/3)*M-A8-A10$	$3*M+A8+A10-3*A6-2*A3-A7-2*A4-2*A5$
A1	$2*A6+2*A3+A7+2*A4+2*A5-A8-2*M-A10$	$A8+(10/3)*M+A10-2*A6-2*A3-A7-2*A4-2*A5-A1-A2$	A2	$(1/3)*M$	$2*A5+2*A3+A7+2*A4+2*A6+A1-3*M$	$(11/3)*M-A1-2*A5-2*A3-A7-2*A4-2*A6$	$A10+A8+A9-(2/3)*M$	$(4/3)*M-A10-A8-A9$
$A8-(1/3)*M+A10$	$3*A6+2*A3+A7+2*A4+2*A5-(7/3)*M-A8-A10$	A1	$(2/3)*M-A6$	$(11/3)*M-A1-2*A5-2*A3-A7-2*A4-2*A6$	$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$	$(5/3)*M+2*A10-5*A6+3*A8-2*A3-A7-2*A4-2*A5$	$2*A3+A7+2*A4+2*A5-2*A10-M+5*A6-3*A8$
M-A10-A8	$3*M+A8+A10-3*A6-2*A3-A7-2*A4-2*A5$	$(2/3)*M-A1$	A6	$2*A5+2*A3+A7+2*A4+2*A6+A1-3*M$	$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$	$(2/3)*M-A10$	A10
A8	$A10-2*A6+2*A8-M$	A9	$3*M+A8+A10-3*A6-2*A3-A7-2*A4-2*A5$	$(4/3)*M-A10-A8-A9$	$5*A6-3*A8+2*A3+A7+2*A4+2*A5-2*A10-M$	A10	$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$
$(2/3)*M-A8$	$(5/3)*M-A10+2*A6-2*A8$	$(2/3)*M-A9$	$3*A6+2*A3+A7+2*A4+2*A5-(7/3)*M-A8-A10$	$A10+A8-2*(1/3)*M+A9$	$(5/3)*M+2*A10-5*A6+3*A8-2*A3-A7-2*A4-2*A5$	$(2/3)*M-A10$	$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$

• Details

It is a *cornered pandiagonal magic square* of order 9, where another *cornered pandiagonal magic squares* of orders 7 and are at the upper left corners having magic square of order 3 at the upper-left corner. In each case, the magic rectangles of orders 2×5 and 2×7 are of equal sums. The magic sums of orders 5, 7 and 9 are given as $T_{5 \times 5} = \frac{5}{3} \times M$, $T_{7 \times 7} = \frac{5}{3} \times M$ and $T_{9 \times 9} = 3 \times M$ where M is the magic sum of order 3. Moreover, the magic squares of orders 5, 7 and 9 are all *pandiagonal*. See below two examples:

Example 5.6. Let's consider following two examples of *pandiagonal magic squares* of order 9 based on the Result 5.6:

9x9	pan	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90
90	10	12	8	11	9	-8	28	2	18	90	99	11	12	10	11	11	-5	27	4	18	99
90	8	10	12	35	-15	-21	41	26	-6	90	99	10	11	12	29	-7	-12	34	31	-9	99
90	12	8	10	-18	38	9	11	1	19	90	99	12	10	11	-8	30	11	11	3	19	99
90	9	-15	38	10	8	16	4	41	-21	90	99	11	-7	30	11	10	16	6	34	-12	99
90	11	35	-18	12	10	54	-34	37	-17	90	99	11	29	-8	12	11	45	-23	35	-13	99
90	28	41	11	4	-34	10	10	-37	57	90	99	27	34	11	6	-23	11	11	-32	54	99
90	-8	-21	9	16	54	10	10	0	20	90	99	-5	-12	11	16	45	11	11	2	20	99
90	18	-6	19	-21	-17	57	20	10	10	90	99	18	-9	19	-12	-13	54	20	11	11	99
	2	26	1	41	37	-37	0	10	10	90		4	31	3	34	35	-32	2	11	11	99
©IJT	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	©IJT	99	99	99	99	99	99	99	99	99	99

The magic sum of magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9 for the first example are 30, 50, 70 and 90, and for the second example are 33, 55, 77 and 99 respectively. Moreover, in each case, the magic rectangles of orders 2×3 , and 2×7 and 2×9 are of equal sums.

Result 5.7. Let's consider following *self-made algebraic pandiagonal magic square* of order 9:

$M-A_2-A_3$	$A_1-A_2+M/3$	$M/3$	$A_2+A_3-A_1$	A_2	$A_4-(1/3)*M+A_8$	$M-A_4-A_8$	A_4	$(2/3)*M-A_4$
$2*A_2+A_3-A_1-(1/3)*M$	$A_2+A_3-(1/3)*M$	$(2/3)*M-A_3$	$2*M/3-A_2$	$A_1-2*A_2+M-A_3$	$A_5-(1/3)*M+A_7$	$M-A_5-A_7$	A_5	$(2/3)*M-A_5$
$M/3$	$(4/3)*M-2*A_2-A_3$	$M/3$	$2*A_2+A_3-(2/3)*M$	$M/3$	$2*A_2+A_3-(2/3)*M$	$(4/3)*M-2*A_2-A_3$	A_6	$(2/3)*M-A_6$
A_1	A_2	A_3	$M-A_2-A_3$	$2*M/3-A_1$	$M-A_5-A_7$	$A_5-(1/3)*M+A_7$	$M-A_5-A_7$	$A_5-(1/3)*M+A_7$
$2*M/3-A_2$	$M/3+A_2-A_1$	$M/3$	$(2/3)*M-A_2-A_3+A_1$	$A_2+A_3-(1/3)*M$	$2*M-A_4-A_8-2*A_2-A_3$	$A_4-(4/3)*M+A_8+2*A_2+A_3$	$(4/3)*M-A_4-A_6-A_8$	$A_4+A_6+A_8-(2/3)*M$
$(5/3)*M-A_4-A_8-A_2-A_3$	$M-A_5-A_7$	A_3	$A_5-(1/3)*M+A_7$	$A_4-(2/3)*M+A_8+A_2$	$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$	A_7	$(2/3)*M-A_7$
$A_4-M+A_8+A_2+A_3$	$A_5-(1/3)*M+A_7$	$(2/3)*M-A_3$	$M-A_5-A_7$	$(4/3)*M-A_2-A_4-A_8$	$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$	A_8	$(2/3)*M-A_8$
$(4/3)*M-A_3-A_2-A_4$	$(2/3)*M-A_5$	$2*A_3+2*A_2-A_6-(2/3)*M$	$A_5-(1/3)*M+A_7$	$A_6+A_4+A_8-A_3-A_2$	$(2/3)*M-A_7$	$(2/3)*M-A_8$	$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$
$A_3+A_2+A_4-(2/3)*M$	A_5	$(4/3)*M-2*A_3-2*A_2+A_6$	$M-A_5-A_7$	$A_3+A_2-A_6-A_4+(2/3)*M-A_8$	A_7	A_8	$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$

• Details

It is a *cornered pandiagonal magic square* of order 9, where another *cornered pandiagonal magic squares* of orders 7 and 5 are at the upper left corners having magic square of order 5 as *single-digit bordered pandiagonal magic square* embedded with magic square of order 3. In each case, the magic rectangles of orders 2×5 and 2×7 are of equal sums. The magic sums of orders 5, 7 and 9 are given as $T_{5 \times 5} = \frac{5}{3} \times M$, $T_{7 \times 7} = \frac{5}{3} \times M$ and $T_{9 \times 9} = 3 \times M$, where M is the magic sum of order 3. Moreover, the magic squares of orders 5, 7 and 9 are all *pandiagonal*. See below two examples:

Example 5.7. Let's consider following two examples of *pandiagonal magic squares* of order 9 based on the Result 5.7:

9x9	pan	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	9x9	pan	99	99	99	99	99	99	99	99	99
108	-9	11	12	24	22	40	-16	24	0	108	99	-12	10	11	24	22	41	-19	24	-2	99
108	34	33	1	2	-10	40	-16	25	-1	108	99	35	34	-1	0	-13	41	-19	25	-3	99
108	12	-19	12	43	12	43	-19	26	-2	108	99	11	-23	11	45	11	45	-23	26	-4	99
108	21	22	23	-9	3	-16	40	-16	40	108	99	21	22	23	-12	1	-19	41	-19	41	99
108	2	13	12	0	33	-47	71	-30	54	108	99	0	12	11	-2	34	-53	75	-34	56	99
108	-37	-16	23	40	50	12	12	27	-3	108	99	-42	-19	23	41	52	11	11	27	-5	99
108	61	40	1	-16	-26	12	12	28	-4	108	99	64	41	-1	-19	-30	11	11	28	-6	99
108	-21	-1	40	40	33	-3	-4	12	12	108	99	-25	-3	42	41	33	-5	-6	11	11	99
	45	25	-16	-16	-9	27	28	12	12	108		47	25	-20	-19	-11	27	28	11	11	99
©IJT	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	©IJT	99	99	99	99	99	99	99	99	99	99

The magic sum of magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9 for the first example are 36, 60, 84 and 108, and for the second example are 33, 55, 77 and 99 respectively. The magic rectangles of each type, i.e., 2×5 and 2×7 are of equal sums.

Result 5.8. Let's consider following *self-made algebraic pandiagonal* magic square of order 9:

A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4	A7	$(2/5)*S-A7$	$(1/5)*S+A1-A9$	$(1/5)*S-A1+A9$
S-A8-A4-A7-A2	A5	A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-(1/5)*S	A6	$(1/5)*S+A8-A1+A7-A3$	$(2/5)*S-A11$	A11	$(3/5)*S-A11-A12$	A11+A12-(1/5)*S
A2+A3+A4-A5-(1/5)*S	A8+A6-A1-A2+A7+(1/5)*S-A3	$(1/5)*S$	A5+S-A8-A4-A7-A2-A3	A1+A2+A3-A6-(1/5)*S	$(3/5)*S-A8-A7$	A7+A8-(1/5)*S	A10	$(2/5)*S-A10$
$(1/5)*S-A3+A5$	$(4/5)*S+A1-A8-A4-A7-A6$	A2+A3-(1/5)*S	A8+A4+A7-A5-A1	$(1/5)*S-A2+A6$	A11	$(2/5)*S-A11$	A11	$(2/5)*S-A11$
A8+A7-A1	A3+A4-A5	$(1/5)*S-A2-A3+A5+A6$	A1+A2-A6	$(4/5)*S-A8-A4-A7$	A8	$(2/5)*S-A8$	$(3/5)*S-A10-A7$	A10+A7-(1/5)*S
$(1/5)*S+A1-A7$	A1+(2/5)*S-A8+A11-A4-A7	$(3/5)*S-A4-A1$	A8+A4+A7-A11-A1	A4+A7-(1/5)*S	$(1/5)*S$	$(1/5)*S$	A12	$(2/5)*S-A12$
$(1/5)*S-A1+A7$	A8+A7+A4-A11-A1	A4+A1-(1/5)*S	A1+(2/5)*S-A8+A11-A4-A7	$(3/5)*S-A4-A7$	$(1/5)*S$	$(1/5)*S$	(A9+A7-A1)	$(2/5)*S-A9-A7+A1$
A9	$(1/5)*S+A11+A12+A1-A8-A7-A4$	$(6/5)*S-A8-A7-A4-A10-A1$	A8+A7+A4-A11-A1	A8-(4/5)*S+2*A7+A4+A10	$(2/5)*S-A12$	$(2/5)*S-A9-A7+A1$	$(1/5)*S$	$(1/5)*S$
$(2/5)*S-A9$	A8+A7+A4+(1/5)*S-A11-A12-A1	A10+A1+A8+A7+A4-(4/5)*S	A1+(2/5)*S-A8+A11-A4-A7	$(6/5)*S-2*A7-A4-A10-A8$	A12	A9+A7-A1	$(1/5)*S$	$(1/5)*S$

• Details

It is a *cornered pandiagonal* magic square of order 9, where another *cornered pandiagonal* magic squares of orders 7 and 5 are at the upper left corners. In each case, the magic rectangles of orders 2×5 and 2×7 are of equal sums. The magic sums of orders 7 and 9 are given as $T_{7 \times 7} = \frac{7}{5} \times S$ and $T_{9 \times 9} = \frac{7}{5} \times S$, where S is the magic sum of order 5. Moreover, the magic squares of orders 5, 7 and 9 are all *pandiagonal*. See below two examples:

Example 5.8. Let's consider following two examples of *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 9 based on the Result 5.8:

9x9	pan	72	72	72	72	72	72	72	72	72	9x9	pan	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81
72	11	13	-16	15	17	23	-7	-8	24	72	81	11	13	-11	15	17	23	-5	-7	25	81
72	-38	19	8	21	30	-15	31	-40	56	72	81	-33	19	7	21	31	-13	31	-37	55	81
72	18	38	8	-34	10	-24	40	29	-13	72	81	17	39	9	-29	9	-21	39	29	-11	81
72	12	-43	20	35	16	31	-15	31	-15	72	81	13	-39	19	35	17	31	-13	31	-13	81
72	37	13	20	3	-33	25	-9	-28	44	72	81	37	13	21	3	-29	25	-7	-25	43	81
72	-4	-7	-4	23	32	8	8	33	-17	72	81	-3	-5	-1	23	31	9	9	33	-15	81
72	20	23	20	-7	-16	8	8	39	-23	72	81	21	23	19	-5	-13	9	9	39	-21	81
72	27	18	-57	23	85	-17	-23	8	8	72	81	27	19	-51	23	81	-15	-21	9	9	81
	-11	-2	73	-7	-69	33	39	8	8	72		-9	-1	69	-5	-63	33	39	9	9	81
©IJT	72	72	72	72	72	72	72	72	72	72	©IJT	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81

The magic sum of magic squares of orders 5, 7 and 9 for the first example are 40, 56 and 72, and for the second example are 45, 63 and 81 respectively. The magic rectangles of each type, i.e., 2×5 and 2×7 are of equal sums.

Result 5.9. *Let's consider following self-made algebraic pandiagonal magic square of order 9:*

$A_{16}+A_{21}-(1/7)*T$	$(4/7)*T+A_{17}+A_{23}-A_{10}+A_{16}-A_3-2*A_4-A_6-A_2-A_{11}-A_1-A_9+A_{21}$	A1	A6	$(8/7)*T+A_{22}-A_{24}-A_{17}-2*A_{23}-A_{13}-A_{14}+A_{10}-2*A_{16}+A_3+2*A_4+A_2+A_{11}+A_9-A_{15}-A_{20}-A_{12}-2*A_{21}$	$A_{24}+A_{17}+A_{23}+A_{13}+A_{14}+A_{16}+A_{15}+A_{20}+A_{12}+A_{19}+A_{21}-(9/7)*T-A_{22}$	$(5/7)*T-A_{17}-A_{16}-A_{19}-A_{21}$	A21	$(2/7)*T-A_{21}$
$A_{24}+A_{17}+A_{23}+A_{13}+A_{10}+A_4+A_{11}-A_7-A_8+A_{12}+A_{19}-(4/7)*T$	$A_{10}+(9/7)*T-2*A_{24}+A_{11}-6*A_{21}-4*A_{16}-(12/7)*T+A_5-2*A_{13}+4*A_3+3*A_4+4*A_6-3*A_{12}+4*A_2-2*A_{18}-3*A_{19}+A_{14}+4*A_1+4*A_7+5*A_9-4*A_{23}-4*A_{17}+4*A_8-2*A_{20}$	A2	A7	$(8/7)*T+A_{24}+3*A_{17}+3*A_{23}+A_{13}-A_{14}-A_{10}+3*A_{16}-A_5-3*A_3-2*A_4-4*A_6-4*A_2-A_{11}-4*A_1-4*A_7-4*A_9+2*A_{20}-3*A_8+3*A_{12}+2*A_{19}+5*A_{21}+2*A_{18}$	$A_{24}+A_{23}+A_{13}+A_{14}-A_{10}+A_{16}-A_3-2*A_4-A_2-A_{11}-A_9+A_{15}+A_{21}-(1/7)*T$	$T-A_{24}-A_{23}-A_{13}-A_{14}-A_{15}-A_{12}$	A22	$(2/7)*T-A_{22}$
$(6/7)*T+A_{24}+3*A_{17}+3*A_2+3*A_{13}-A_{14}-A_{10}+3*A_{16}-A_5-3*A_3-2*A_4-3*A_6-3*A_2-A_{11}-4*A_1-3*A_7-4*A_9+2*A_{20}-3*A_8+2*A_{12}+2*A_{19}+5*A_2+1+2*A_{18}$	$A_{24}+3*A_{17}+2*A_{23}+A_{13}-A_{14}+3*A_{16}-2*A_3-A_4-3*A_6-3*A_2-3*A_1-3*A_7-3*A_9+2*A_{20}-3*A_8+2*A_{12}+3*A_{19}+5*A_{21}+2*A_{18}-(1/7)*T$	$2*A_{24}+4*A_{17}+4*A_{23}+2*A_{13}-A_{10}+4*A_{16}-A_5-3*A_3-3*A_4-3*A_6-4*A_2-4*A_1-4*A_7-4*A_9+3*A_{20}-3*A_8+3*A_{12}+3*A_{19}+6*A_{21}+2*A_{18}-(1/7)*T-A_{22}$	$(3/7)*T-A_{24}-4*A_{17}-3*A_{23}-A_{13}+A_{14}-3*A_{16}+3*A_3+2*A_4+3*A_6+3*A_2+4*A_1+3*A_7+3*A_9-2*A_{20}+3*A_8-3*A_{12}-3*A_{19}-5*A_{21}-2*A_{18}$	$A_{10}-2*A_{16}+A_5+2*A_3+2*A_4+3*A_6+3*A_2+3*A_1+3*A_7+4*A_9-2*A_{20}+3*A_8-2*A_{12}-2*A_{19}-4*A_{21}-2*A_{18}-(4/7)*T-A_{24}-2*A_{17}-2*A_{23}-A_{13}$	$(4/7)*T+A_{22}-2*A_{24}-4*A_{17}-4*A_{23}-2*A_{13}+A_{14}+A_{10}-5*A_{16}+A_5+3*A_3+2*A_4+3*A_6+4*A_2+A_{11}+4*A_1+4*A_7+4*A_9-3*A_{20}+3*A_8-3*A_{12}-3*A_{19}-7*A_{21}-2*A_{18}$	A12	A23	$(2/7)*T-A_{23}$
$(1/7)*T-A_{24}-4*A_{17}-3*A_{23}-2*A_{13}+A_{14}-3*A_{16}+3*A_3+2*A_4+3*A_6+3*A_2+4*A_1+4*A_7+4*A_9-2*A_{20}+4*A_8-3*A_{12}-3*A_{19}-5*A_{21}-2*A_{18}$	$(3/7)*T+A_{22}-A_{24}-4*A_{17}-3*A_{23}-A_{13}+A_{14}+A_{10}-4*A_{16}+A_5+2*A_3+2*A_4+3*A_6+3*A_2+4*A_1+3*A_7+3*A_9-3*A_{20}+3*A_8-2*A_{12}-3*A_{19}-6*A_{21}-2*A_{18}$	$(8/7)*T+A_{22}-2*A_{24}-4*A_{17}-4*A_{23}-2*A_{13}+A_{10}-4*A_{16}+2*A_3+2*A_4+3*A_6+3*A_2+3*A_1+4*A_7+4*A_9-3*A_{20}+3*A_8-3*A_{12}-3*A_{19}-6*A_{21}-2*A_{18}$	$(4/7)*T+A_{24}+4*A_{17}+3*A_{23}+A_{13}-A_{14}-A_{10}+3*A_{16}-3*A_3-2*A_4-4*A_6-3*A_2-4*A_1-4*A_7-4*A_9+3*A_{12}+3*A_{19}+5*A_{21}+2*A_{18}$	$2*A_{24}+4*A_{17}+4*A_{23}+2*A_{13}+4*A_{16}-2*A_3-2*A_4-2*A_6-3*A_2-3*A_1-3*A_7-3*A_9+3*A_{20}-3*A_8+3*A_{12}+3*A_{19}+6*A_{21}+2*A_{18}-(10/7)*T-A_{22}$	$(1/7)*T-A_{22}+A_{24}+4*A_{17}+3*A_{23}+A_{13}-A_{14}-A_{10}+4*A_{16}-A_5-2*A_3-2*A_4-3*A_6-3*A_2-4*A_1-4*A_7-4*A_9+3*A_{20}-3*A_8+2*A_{12}+3*A_{19}+6*A_{21}+2*A_{18}$	A13	$A_{16}+A_3+A_4+A_6+A_2+A_1+A_7+A_9+A_{20}+A_8-A_{12}+A_{21}v$	$(9/7)*T+A_{22}+A_{13}-A_{16}-A_3-A_4-A_6-A_2-A_1-A_7-A_9-A_{20}-A_8+A_{12}-A_{21}$
$A_{24}+2*A_{17}+2*A_{23}+A_{13}-A_{10}+2*A_{16}-A_3-2*A_4-A_6-A_2-A_{11}-A_1-A_7-A_9+A_{15}+A_{20}-A_8+A_{12}+A_{19}+2*A_{21}-(3/7)*T-A_{22}$	$A_{24}+5*A_{17}+4*A_{23}+2*A_{13}-A_{14}-A_{10}+4*A_{16}-3*A_3-3*A_4-3*A_6-3*A_2-4*A_1-4*A_7-4*A_9+3*A_{20}-4*A_8+3*A_{12}+3*A_{19}+6*A_{21}+2*A_{18}-(1/7)*T-A_{22}$	A3	A8	$(6/7)*T+A_{22}-2*A_{24}-6*A_{17}-5*A_{23}-2*A_{13}+A_{14}+A_{10}-5*A_{16}+3*A_3+3*A_4+4*A_6+4*A_2+5*A_1+5*A_7+4*A_9-3*A_{20}+4*A_8-4*A_{12}-4*A_{19}-7*A_{21}-2*A_{18}$	$(5/7)*T+A_{22}-A_{17}-A_{23}-A_{13}-A_{14}+A_{10}-A_{16}+2*A_4+A_{11}+A_9-A_{15}-A_{20}-A_{21}$	A14	A24	$(2/7)*T-A_{24}$
$(3/7)*T+A_{22}-A_{24}-2*A_{17}-2*A_{23}-A_{13}+A_{10}-2*A_{16}+A_5+A_3+A_4+A_6+A_2+A_{11}+A_1+A_7+A_9-A_{15}-A_{20}+A_8-A_{12}-A_{19}-2*A_{21}$	$A_{10}-A_5+A_3+2*A_4+A_6+A_2+A_{11}+A_1+A_7+A_9-A_{15}+A_8-A_{12}-(2/7)*T-A_{17}-A_{23}-A_{13}$	A4	A9	$A_{24}+2*A_{17}+2*A_{23}+A_{13}+A_{14}-2*A_{10}+2*A_{16}-A_3-3*A_4-A_6-A_2-A_{11}-A_1-A_7-2*A_9+A_{15}+A_{20}-A_8+A_{12}+A_{19}+2*A_{21}-(1/7)*T-A_{22}$	$T+A_{17}+A_{23}+A_{13}-A_{14}-A_3-A_4-A_6-A_2-A_{11}-A_1-A_7-A_9-A_8+A_{12}$	A15	$(10/7)*T+A_{13}-A_{16}-A_3-A_4-A_6-A_2-A_1-A_7-A_9-A_{20}-A_8+A_{12}-A_{21}$	$A_{16}+A_3+A_4+A_6+A_2+A_1+A_7+A_9+A_{20}+A_8-A_{12}+A_{21}-(8/7)*T-A_{13}$
$(5/7)*T-A_{24}-A_{23}-A_{16}-A_{21}$	$T+A_{24}+A_{23}+A_{13}-A_{10}-A_5-A_3-A_4-A_6-A_2-A_{11}-A_1-A_7-A_9+A_{15}-A_8+A_{12}$	A5	A10	A11	$A_3+A_4+A_6+A_2+A_1+A_7+A_9-A_{15}+A_8-A_{12}-A_{19}-A_{24}-A_{17}-A_{23}-A_{13}$	$A_{24}+A_{17}+A_{23}+A_{16}+A_{19}+A_{21}-(5/7)*T$	$(4/7)*T-A_{24}-A_{23}-A_{21}$	$A_{24}+A_{23}+A_{21}-(2/7)*T$
A16	$A_{24}+2*A_{17}+2*A_{23}+A_{13}+2*A_1-6-A_3-A_4-A_6-A_2-A_1-A_7-A_9-A_8+A_{12}+A_{19}+2*A_{21}-(2/7)*T-A_{22}$	A17	$(5/7)*T+A_{22}-A_{24}-2*A_{17}-2*A_{23}-A_{13}-2*A_{16}+A_3+A_4+A_6+A_2+A_1+A_7+A_9-A_{20}+A_8-A_{12}-A_{19}-2*A_{21}$	A19	A20	$(4/7)*T-A_{17}-A_{16}-A_{19}$	$(1/7)*T$	$(1/7)*T$
$(2/7)*T-A_{16}$	$(4/7)*T+A_{22}-A_{24}-2*A_{17}-2*A_{23}-A_{13}-2*A_{16}+A_3+A_4+A_6+A_2+A_1+A_7+A_9+A_8-A_{12}-A_{19}-2*A_{21}$	$(2/7)*T-A_{17}$	$A_{24}+2*A_{17}+2*A_{23}+A_{13}+2*A_1-6-A_3-A_4-A_6-A_2-A_1-A_7-A_9+A_{20}-A_8+A_{12}+A_{19}+2*A_{21}-(3/7)*T-A_{22}$	$(2/7)*T-A_{19}$	$(2/7)*T-A_{20}$	$A_{17}+A_{16}+A_{19}-(2/7)*T$	$(1/7)*T$	$(1/7)*T$

• Details

It is a cornered pandiagonal magic square of order 9, where pandiagonal magic squares of orders 7 is at the upper-left corner. In this case, the magic rectangles of orders 2×7 are of equal sums. The magic sum of order is given as $T_{9 \times 9} = \frac{9}{7} \times T$, where T is the magic sum of order 7. Both the magic squares of orders 7 and 9 are pandiagonal. See below two examples:

Example 5.9. *Let's consider following two examples of pandiagonal magic squares of order 9 based on the Result 5.9:*

9x9	pan	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	9x9	pan	117	117	117	117	117	117	117	117	117
126	113	97	11	26	-438	470	-181	71	-43	126	117	114	93	11	26	-446	479	-186	71	-45	117
126	354	-1174	14	29	893	235	-253	74	-46	126	117	358	-1171	14	29	885	236	-260	74	-48	117
126	890	965	1313	-1069	-718	-1327	44	77	-49	126	117	884	966	1314	-1072	-714	-1331	44	77	-51	117
126	-1048	-1102	-1300	1007	1400	1094	47	116	-88	126	117	-1049	-1105	-1308	1003	1410	1093	47	123	-97	117
126	484	1247	17	32	-1549	-183	50	80	-52	126	117	487	1248	17	32	-1555	-188	50	80	-54	117
126	-481	-48	20	35	469	50	53	-148	176	126	117	-484	-46	20	35	470	43	53	-158	184	117
126	-214	113	23	38	41	-241	338	-172	200	126	117	-219	106	23	38	41	-241	343	-176	202	117
126	56	476	59	-502	65	68	-124	14	14	126	117	56	478	59	-507	65	68	-128	13	13	117
	-28	-448	-31	530	-37	-40	152	14	14	126		-30	-452	-33	533	-39	-42	154	13	13	117
©IJT	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	©IJT	117	117	117	117	117	117	117	117	117	117

The magic sum of magic squares of orders 7 and 9 for the first example are 98 and 126, and for the second example are 91 and 117 respectively. The magic rectangles of order 2×7 are of equal sums.

Result 5.10. Let's consider following *self-made algebraic pandiagonal magic square* of order 9:

S/5	$3*S/5-A7-A1$	$2*S/5-A6$	$3*A1+3*A7-A8-2*A6$	A6	$A8+2*A6-2*A1-2*A7$	S/5	A11	$(2/5)*S-A11$
A7	A1	A2	$4*S/5-3*A1-A2-A3+A8+2*A6-3*A7$	A3	$S/5-A8-2*A6+2*A1+3*A7$	$2*S/5-A7$	$A1+3*A7-(1/5)*S-A6+A10$	$(3/5)*S+A6-A10-A1-3*A7$
$2*S/5-A8$	$A8+S/5+A6-A1-A2$	A4	$3*A1+A2+A3-A8-2*A6+3*A7-A4-A5$	A5	$4*S/5-2*A1-A3+A6-3*A7$	A8	$(2/5)*S-A9$	A9
$2*S/5+A6-A1-3*A7$	$A2+A3-A8-2*A6+2*A1+3*A7-A4$	$4*S/5-2*A1-A2-A3+A6-3*A7+A5$	$(1/5)*S$	$A8+S/5+A6-A1-A2-A3+A4$	$A1+A2+A3-A5-S/5$	$A1+3*A7-A6$	$(2/5)*S-A1+A6-3*A7$	$A1-A6+3*A7$
A8	$S/5-A3+A4$	$A8+A6-A5$	$A2+A3-S/5$	$4*S/5-A4-A8-A6$	$S/5-A2+A5$	$2*S/5-A8$	A9	$(2/5)*S-A9$
$S/5-A6+A1+2*A7$	$3*S/5+A6-2*A1-3*A7$	$A3+S/5-A8-2*A6+2*A1+3*A7-A4$	$S/5-A2-A3+A4+A5$	$A1+A2-A5$	$A8+A6-A1$	$S/5+A6-A1-2*A7$	$(2/5)*S-A10$	A10
S/5	$A7+A1-S/5$	A6	$2*S/5+A8+2*A6-3*A1-3*A7$	$2*S/5-A6$	$2*S/5-A8-2*A6+2*A1+2*A7$	S/5	$(2/5)*S-A11$	A11
$(2/5)*S-A11$	$A6-3*A7+(4/5)*S-A10-2*A1$	$(2/5)*S+A9-A6-A8$	$3*A1-2*A6+3*A7-A8$	$A6-A9+A8$	$A6+A8+A10-(1/5)*S-A1$	A11	$(1/5)*S$	$(1/5)*S$
A11	$2*A1-A6+3*A7+A10-(2/5)*S$	$A6-A9+A8$	$(2/5)*S-3*A1+2*A6-3*A7+A8$	$(2/5)*S+A9-A6-A8$	$(3/5)*S+A1-A6-A8-A10$	$(2/5)*S-A11$	$(1/5)*S$	$(1/5)*S$

• Details

It is a *cornered pandiagonal magic square* of order 9, where *single-digit pandiagonal magic square* of order 7 is at the upper-left corner embedded with a *pandiagonal magic square* of order 5. The magic rectangles of order 2×7 are of equal sums. The magic sum of orders 7 and 9 are given as $T_{7 \times 7} = \frac{7}{5} \times S$, and $T_{9 \times 9} = \frac{9}{5} \times S$, where S is the magic sum of order 5. The magic squares of orders 5, 7 and 9 are *pandiagonal*. See below two examples:

Example 5.10. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 9 based on the Result 5.10:

9x9	pan	54	54	54	54	54	54	54	54	54	9x9	pan	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45
54	6	-10	-4	34	16	-6	6	21	-9	54	45	5	-13	-6	34	16	-6	5	21	-11	45
54	17	11	12	-35	13	29	-5	60	-48	54	45	17	11	12	-39	13	28	-7	61	-51	45
54	-6	17	14	30	15	-46	18	-7	19	54	45	-8	16	14	30	15	-50	18	-9	19	45
54	-34	34	-43	6	18	15	46	-34	46	54	45	-36	34	-47	5	17	16	46	-36	46	45
54	18	7	19	19	-24	9	-6	19	-7	54	45	18	6	19	20	-28	8	-8	19	-9	45
54	35	-39	28	10	8	23	-23	-8	20	54	45	34	-42	27	9	8	23	-24	-10	20	45
54	6	22	16	-22	-4	18	6	-9	21	54	45	5	23	16	-24	-6	16	5	-11	21	45
54	-9	-53	-3	34	15	37	21	6	6	54	45	-11	-57	-5	34	15	38	21	5	5	45
	21	65	15	-22	-3	-25	-9	6	6	54		21	67	15	-24	-5	-28	-11	5	5	45
©IJT	54	54	54	54	54	54	54	54	54	54	©IJT	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45

The magic sums of magic squares of orders 5, 7 and 9 for the first example are 25, 35 and 45, and for the second example are 30, 42 and 54 respectively. The magic rectangles of order 2×7 are of equal sums.

Result 5.11. Let's consider following *self-made algebraic pandiagonal magic square* of order 9:

$(1/3)*M$	M	$(2/3)*M-A2$	$-(1/3)*M$	A2	$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$	A3	$(2/3)*M-A3$
$-(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$	A1	$2*M/3-A1$	M	$2*M/3-M$	M	(-A4)	$(2/3)*M+A4$
A2	$(2/3)*M-A1$	M/3	A1	M/3	M/3	$(2/3)*M-A2$	0	$(2/3)*M$
M	A1	$(2/3)*M-A1$	$(1/3)*M$	(-A1)	$(2/3)*M+A1$	$-(1/3)*M$	M	$-(1/3)*M$
$(2/3)*M-A2$	$-(1/3)*M$	M/3	$M+A1-M/3$	$(1/3)*M$	$(2/3)*M-A1$	A2	$(2/3)*M$	0
$(1/3)*M$	M	M/3	(-A1)	A1	$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$	A4	$(2/3)*M-A4$
$(1/3)*M$	$-(1/3)*M$	A2	M	$(2/3)*M-A2$	$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$	$(2/3)*M-A3$	A3
$(2/3)*M-A3$	$(2/3)*M+A4$	$(2/3)*M$	$-(1/3)*M$	0	$(2/3)*M-A4$	A3	$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$
A3	(-A4)	0	M	$(2/3)*M$	A4	$(2/3)*M-A3$	$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$

• Details

It is a *cornered pandiagonal magic square* of order 9, where *single-digit pandiagonal magic square* of order 7 is at the upper-left corner embedded with a *cornered pandiagonal magic square* of order 5 having magic square of order 3 at upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of order 2×7 are of equal sums. The magic sum of orders 5, 7 and 9 are given as $T_{5 \times 5} = \frac{5}{3} \times M$, $T_{7 \times 7} = \frac{7}{3} \times M$, and $T_{9 \times 9} = 3 \times M$, where M is the magic sum of order 3. The magic squares of orders 5, 7 and 9 are *pandiagonal*. See below two examples:

Example 5.11. Let's consider following two examples of *pandiagonal magic squares* of order 9 based on the Result 5.11:

9x9	pan	72	72	72	72	72	72	72	72	72	9x9	pan	63	63	63	63	63	63	63	63	63
72	8	24	1	-8	15	8	8	19	-3	72	63	7	21	-1	-7	15	7	7	19	-5	63
72	-8	8	11	5	24	-8	24	-23	39	72	63	-7	7	11	3	21	-7	21	-23	37	63
72	15	5	8	11	8	8	1	0	16	72	63	15	3	7	11	7	7	-1	0	14	63
72	24	11	5	8	-11	27	-8	24	-8	72	63	21	11	3	7	-11	25	-7	21	-7	63
72	1	-8	8	27	8	5	15	16	0	72	63	-1	-7	7	25	7	3	15	14	0	63
72	8	24	8	-11	11	8	8	23	-7	72	63	7	21	7	-11	11	7	7	23	-9	63
72	8	-8	15	24	1	8	8	-3	19	72	63	7	-7	15	21	-1	7	7	-5	19	63
72	-3	39	16	-8	0	-7	19	8	8	72	63	-5	37	14	-7	0	-9	19	7	7	63
	19	-23	0	24	16	23	-3	8	8	72		19	-23	0	21	14	23	-5	7	7	63
©IJT	72	72	72	72	72	72	72	72	72	72	©IJT	63	63	63	63	63	63	63	63	63	63

The magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9 for the first example are 24, 40, 56 and 72, and for the second example are 21, 35, 49 and 63 respectively. The magic rectangles of order 2×7 are of equal sums.

Result 5.12. Let's consider following *self-made algebraic pandiagonal magic square* of order 9:

M/3	M-A3-M/3	(1/3)*M-3*A3+A2	A2	3*A3+(1/3)*M-A2	M/3+A3-A2	M/3	A4	(2/3)*M-A4
A3	M/3	A1-A2+M/3	M/3	(2/3)*M-A1	A2	(2/3)*M-A3	(1/3)*M+A2-A5	(1/3)*M-A2+A5
3*A3+(1/3)*M-A2	(1/3)*M+A2-A1	(1/3)*M	A2	2*M/3-A2	A1-A2+M/3	(1/3)*M-3*A3+A2	A2	(2/3)*M-A2
(2/3)*M-A2	M/3	(2/3)*M-A2	M/3	A2	M/3	A2	(2/3)*M-A2	A2
(1/3)*M-3*A3+A2	A1	A2	(2/3)*M-A2	M/3	2*M/3-A1	3*A3+(1/3)*M-A2	(2/3)*M-A2	A2
(1/3)*M-A3+A2	2*M/3-A2	M/3+A2-A1	M/3	A1	(1/3)*M	A3+M/3-A2	A5	(2/3)*M-A5
(1/3)*M	A3	3*A3+(1/3)*M-A2	(2/3)*M-A2	(1/3)*M-3*A3+A2	(1/3)*M-A3+A2	(1/3)*M	(2/3)*M-A4	A4
(2/3)*M-A4	(1/3)*M-A2+A5	(2/3)*M-A2	A2	A2	(2/3)*M-A5	A4	(1/3)*M	(1/3)*M
A4	(1/3)*M+A2-A5	A2	(2/3)*M-A2	(2/3)*M-A2	A5	(2/3)*M-A4	(1/3)*M	(1/3)*M

• Details

It is a **cornered pandiagonal** magic square of order 9, where **single-digit pandiagonal** magic square of order 7 is at the upper-left corner embedded with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 and a magic square of order 3 as an inner magic square. The magic rectangles of order 2×7 are of equal sums. The magic sum of orders 5, 7 and 9 are given as $T_{5 \times 5} = \frac{5}{3} \times M$, $T_{7 \times 7} = \frac{7}{3} \times M$, and $T_{9 \times 9} = 3 \times M$, where M is the magic sum of order 3. The magic squares of orders 5, 7 and 9 are **pandiagonal**. See below two examples:

Example 5.12. Let's consider following two examples of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 9 based on the Result 5.12:

Result 5.13. Let's consider following *self-made algebraic pandiagonal magic square* of order 9:

$(1/3)*M$	$A5-M/3+A1$	$5*A1+(7/6)*M-3*A6-3*A7-A4-A8$	$7*A1-3*A6-4*A7+(2/3)*M-2*A4$	$(1/3)*M+A6+A7-2*A1$	$4*A6+5*A7+2*A4-9*A1$	$2*A6+2*A7-(1/2)*M+A4+A8-3*A1$	$A1-A6-A5-A7+M$	$(1/3)*M$
$(2/3)*M-A5$	$(2/3)*M-A1$	$A4$	$A3+A4+3*A6+3*A7-(1/2)*M-5*A1$	$A1-A6-A7+(1/3)*M+A2$	$4*A1-2*A6-2*A7+(7/6)*M-A2-A3-A4$	$2*A1-A6-A7+(2/3)*M-A4$	$A6+A7-A1$	$A5$
$A6+A7+A8-(2/3)*M$	$(1/2)*M-4*A1+2*A6+2*A7$	$A1$	$5*A1-3*A6-3*A7+(7/6)*M-A3-A4$	$(1/3)*M-A1+A6+A7-A2$	$A3+A4-4*A1+2*A6+2*A7+A2-(1/2)*M$	$A1-A6-A7+(2/3)*M$	$2*A1-A6-A7+(1/6)*M$	$(4/3)*M-A8-A6-A7$
$(2/3)*M-A6$	$M+A1-A3-A6-A7$	$A3+A6+A7-(1/3)*M-A1$	$2*A1-(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M-4*A1+2*A6+2*A7$	$2*A1-2*A6-2*A7+M$	$M-A2-A3$	$A2+A3-(1/3)*M$	$A6$
$M-A6-A7$	$A6+A7-A2$	$(2/3)*M+A2-A6-A7$	$(5/3)*M-2*A6-2*A7$	$M/3$	$2*A6+2*A7-M$	$A2$	$(2/3)*M-A2$	$A6+A7-(1/3)*M$
$(2/3)*M-A7$	$A3+A2-A1$	$(2/3)*M+A1-A3-A2$	$2*A6+2*A7-(1/3)*M-2*A1$	$4*A1-2*A6-2*A7+(1/3)*M$	$M-2*A1$	$A3$	$(2/3)*M-A3$	$A7$
$(2/3)*M-A8$	$4*A1-A6-A7-(1/2)*M$	$A6+A7-A1$	$A3+A4+2*A6+2*A7+A2-(1/6)*M-5*A1$	$(1/3)*M+A1-A2$	$4*A1-2*A6-2*A7+(5/6)*M-A3-A4$	$(2/3)*M-A1$	$(7/6)*M-2*A1$	$A8$
$A6+A5+A7-(2/3)*M$	$A1-A6-A7+(2/3)*M$	$(4/3)*M-A6-A7-A4$	$5*A1-A3+(5/6)*M-A4-2*A6-2*A7-A2$	$(1/3)*M-A1+A2$	$A3+A4-4*A1+2*A6+2*A7-(1/6)*M$	$2*A6+2*A7-(2/3)*M+A4-2*A1$	$A1$	$(4/3)*M-A6-A5-A7$
$(1/3)*M$	$M-A1-A5$	$3*A6+3*A7+A4+A8-(1/2)*M-5*A1$	$3*A6+4*A7+2*A4-7*A1$	$(1/3)*M+2*A1-A6-A7$	$(2/3)*M+9*A1-4*A6-5*A7-2*A4$	$(7/6)*M+3*A1-2*A6-2*A7-A4-A8$	$A6+A5+A7-(1/3)*M-A1$	$M/3$

• Details

It is a *single-digit bordered pandiagonal magic square* of order 9 embedded with a *double-digit pandiagonal magic square* of order 7 having magic square of order 3 in the inner part. The magic rectangles of order 2×3 are of equal sums. The magic sum of orders 7 and 9 are given as $T_{7 \times 7} = \frac{7}{3} \times M$, and $T_{9 \times 9} = 3 \times M$, where M is the magic sum of order 3. The magic squares of orders 7 and 9 are *pandiagonal*. See below two examples:

Example 5.13. Let's consider following two examples of *pandiagonal magic squares* of order 9 based on the Result 5.13:

9x9	pan	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	9x9	pan	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126
126	14	28	-114	-128	44	186	112	-30	14	126	126	14	28	-114	-128	44	186	112	-30	14	126
126	1	13	25	131	-13	-76	-27	45	27	126	126	1	13	25	131	-13	-76	-27	45	27	126
126	65	81	15	-103	41	104	-17	-23	-37	126	126	65	81	15	-103	41	104	-17	-23	-37	126
126	-1	-25	53	16	74	-48	2	26	29	126	126	-1	-25	53	16	74	-48	2	26	29	126
126	-18	42	-14	-50	14	78	18	10	46	126	126	-18	42	-14	-50	14	78	18	10	46	126
126	-3	25	3	76	-46	12	22	6	31	126	126	-3	25	3	76	-46	12	22	6	31	126
126	-5	-21	45	103	11	-72	13	19	33	126	126	-5	-21	45	103	11	-72	13	19	33	126
126	59	-17	-29	-75	17	100	87	15	-31	126	126	59	-17	-29	-75	17	100	87	15	-31	126
	14	0	142	156	-16	-158	-84	58	14	126		14	0	142	156	-16	-158	-84	58	14	126
©IJT	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	©IJT	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126

The magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 7 and 9 for the first example are 42, 98 and 126, and for the second example are 48, 112 and 144 respectively. The magic rectangles of order 2×3 are of equal sums.

Result 5.14. Let's consider following *self-made algebraic pandiagonal magic square* of order 9:

$(1/3)*M$	A6	$(4/3)*M-A5-A2-A4$	A7	$A2+A4-(1/3)*M$	A8	A5	$(4/3)*M-A7-A6-A8$	$(1/3)*M$
$(2/3)*M-A6$	M/3	A3	$(2/3)*M-A3$	A1	$(2/3)*M-A1$	M-A7-A8	$A8+A7-(1/3)*M$	A6
$A2+A4+A5-(2/3)*M$	$(2/3)*M-A3$	$(1/3)*M$	A3	A2	$(2/3)*M-A2$	M-A2-A4	$A2+A4-(1/3)*M$	$(4/3)*M-A5-A2-A4$
$(2/3)*M-A7$	A3	$(2/3)*M-A3$	$(1/3)*M$	$(4/3)*M-A1-A3-A2$	$A2-(2/3)*M+A1+A3$	$(2/3)*M-A1$	A1	A7
M-A2-A4	$(2/3)*M-A1$	$(2/3)*M-A2$	$A2-(2/3)*M+A1+A3$	M/3	$(2/3)*M-A3$	A4	$(2/3)*M-A4$	$A2+A4-(1/3)*M$
$(2/3)*M-A8$	A1	A2	$(4/3)*M-A1-A3-A2$	A3	$(1/3)*M$	$A2+A8+A7+A1-M$	$(5/3)*M-A2-A8-A7-A1$	A8
$(2/3)*M-A5$	$A8+A7-(1/3)*M$	$A2+A4-(1/3)*M$	A1	$(2/3)*M-A4$	$(5/3)*M-A2-A8-A7-A1$	$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$	A5
$A6+A8+A7-(2/3)*M$	M-A7-A8	M-A2-A4	$(2/3)*M-A1$	A4	$A2+A8+A7+A1-M$	$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$	$(4/3)*M-A7-A6-A8$
$(1/3)*M$	$(2/3)*M-A6$	$A2+A4+A5-(2/3)*M$	$(2/3)*M-A7$	M-A2-A4	$(2/3)*M-A8$	$(2/3)*M-A5$	$A6+A8+A7-(2/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$

• Details

It is a *single-digit bordered pandiagonal magic square* of order 9 embedded with a *cornered pandiagonal magic square* of order 7 having magic square of orders 5 and at the upper left-corner. In each case, the magic rectangles of order 2×3 , 2×5 are of equal sums. The magic sum of orders 5, 7 and 9 are given as $T_{5 \times 5} = \frac{5}{3} \times M$, $T_{7 \times 7} = \frac{7}{3} \times M$, and $T_{9 \times 9} = 3 \times M$, where M is the magic sum of order 3. The magic squares of orders 5, 7 and 9 are *pandiagonal*. See below two examples:

Example 5.14. Let's consider following two examples of *pandiagonal magic squares* of order 9 based on the Result 5.14:

9x9	pan	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	9x9	pan	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81
108	12	21	-1	23	18	25	19	-21	12	108	81	9	21	-13	23	21	25	19	-33	9	81
108	3	12	15	9	11	13	-12	36	21	108	81	-3	9	15	3	11	7	-21	39	21	81
108	25	9	12	15	13	11	6	18	-1	108	81	31	3	9	15	13	5	-3	21	-13	81
108	1	15	9	12	9	15	13	11	23	108	81	-5	15	3	9	-3	21	7	11	23	81
108	6	13	11	15	12	9	17	7	18	108	81	-3	7	5	21	9	3	17	1	21	81
108	-1	11	13	9	15	12	36	-12	25	108	81	-7	11	13	-3	15	9	45	-27	25	81
108	5	36	18	11	7	-12	12	12	19	108	81	-1	39	21	11	1	-27	9	9	19	81
108	45	-12	6	13	17	36	12	12	-21	108	81	51	-21	-3	7	17	45	9	9	-33	81
	12	3	25	1	6	-1	5	45	12	108		9	-3	31	-5	-3	-7	-1	51	9	81
©IJT	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	©IJT	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81

The magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9 for the first example are 36, 60, 84 and 108, and for the second example are 27, 45, 63 and 81 respectively. The magic rectangles of order 2×3 , 2×5 are of equal sums.

Result 5.15. Let's consider following *self-made algebraic pandiagonal magic square* of order 9:

$(1/5)*S$	$A7+(2/5)*S-A12-$ A1	$(-A7-A11-A9+$ $(4/5)*S-A1+A10)$	$(2/5)*S+A1-A7-$ A9	$A7+A11+A9-$ $(4/5)*S+A8+A1$	A9	$(3/5)*S-A10-A8$	A12	$(1/5)*S$
$(1/5)*S-A7+A12$	A1	A2	$S-A1-A2-A3-A4$	A3	A4	A7	$(2/5)*S-A7$	$A7+(1/5)*S-A12$
$(2/5)*S-A10$	$A7+A11+A9-A2-$ $(1/5)*S$	A5	$A1+A2+A3+A4-$ $A5-A6-(1/5)*S$	A6	$(7/5)*S-A4-A7-$ $A11-A9-A1-A3$	$(2/5)*S-A8$	A8	A10
$(2/5)*S-A11$	A3- $(1/5)*S+A4+A2-$ A5	$(7/5)*S+A6-A1-$ $A2-A3-A4-A7-A11-$ A9	$(1/5)*S$	$A5-(1/5)*S$ $+A7+A11+A9-$ A2-A3	$A1+A2+A3-A6-$ $(1/5)*S$	$A4+A7+A11+A9-$ $(3/5)*S$	$S-A7-A4-A11-$ A9	A11
$(2/5)*S-A8$	$(1/5)*S-A3+A5$	$A1+A7+A11+A9-$ $A6-(2/5)*S$	$A2+A3-(1/5)*S$	$(6/5)*S-A5-A1-$ $A7-A11-A9$	$(1/5)*S-A2+A6$	A8	$(2/5)*S-A8$	A8
$A7+A11-(1/5)*S$	$(6/5)*S+A7-A1-$ $A4-2*A7-A11-$ A9	A3+A4-A5	$(1/5)*S-A2-$ $A3+A5+A6$	A1+A2-A6	$A7+A11+A9-$ $(2/5)*S$	$(6/5)*S-A4-$ $2*A7-A11-A9$	$A4+2*A7+A11+$ $A9-(4/5)*S$	$(3/5)*S-A7-A11$
$A10+A8-(1/5)*S$	$(1/5)*S+A1-A7$	$A7+A11+A9-$ $(4/5)*S+A8+A1$	$(3/5)*S-A4-A1$	$(6/5)*S-A8-A1-$ $A7-A11-A9$	$A4+A7-(1/5)*S$	$(1/5)*S$	$(1/5)*S$	$(3/5)*S-A10-A8$
$(2/5)*S-A12$	$(1/5)*S-A1+A7$	$(6/5)*S-A8-A1-A7-$ A11-A9	$A4+A1-(1/5)*S$	$A7+A11+A9-$ $(4/5)*S+A8+A1$	$(3/5)*S-A4-A7$	$(1/5)*S$	$(1/5)*S$	A12
$(1/5)*S$	$A12+A1-A7$	$A7+A1-(2/5)*S$ $+A9+A11-A10$	$A7+A9-A1$	$(6/5)*S-A8-A1-$ $A7-A11-A9$	$(2/5)*S-A9$	$A10+A8-(1/5)*S$	$2*S-8*S/5-A12$	$S/5$

• Details

It is a *single-digit bordered pandiagonal magic square* of order 9 embedded with a *cornered pandiagonal magic square* of order 7 having *pandiagonal magic square* of orders 5 at the upper left-corner. The magic rectangles of order 2×5 are of equal sums. The magic sum of orders 7 and 9 are given as $T_{7 \times 7} = \frac{7}{5} \times S$, and $T_{9 \times 9} = \frac{9}{5} \times S$, where S is the magic sum of order 5. The magic squares of orders 5, 7 and 9 are *pandiagonal*. See below two examples:

Example 5.15. Let's consider following two examples of *pandiagonal magic squares* of order 9 based on the Result 5.15:

9x9	pan	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	9x9	pan	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81
108	12	-1	-27	-28	95	34	-32	43	12	108	81	9	-7	-39	-34	107	34	-41	43	9	81
108	27	10	13	2	16	19	28	-4	-3	108	81	24	10	13	-13	16	19	28	-10	-6	81
108	-13	77	22	-1	25	-63	-7	31	37	108	81	-19	80	22	2	25	-84	-13	31	37	81
108	-16	14	-51	12	83	2	85	-61	40	108	81	-22	17	-72	9	86	5	94	-76	40	81
108	-7	18	63	17	-62	24	31	-7	31	108	81	-13	15	69	20	-80	21	31	-13	31	81
108	56	-59	13	30	-2	78	-77	101	-32	108	81	59	-77	13	27	-2	84	-95	113	-41	81
108	56	-6	95	7	-71	35	12	12	-32	108	81	59	-9	107	-2	-89	38	9	9	-41	81
108	-19	30	-71	17	95	-11	12	12	43	108	81	-25	27	-89	20	107	-20	9	9	43	81
	12	25	51	52	-71	-10	56	-19	12	108		9	25	57	52	-89	-16	59	-25	9	81
©IJT	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	©IJT	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81

The magic sums of magic squares of orders 5, 7 and 9 for the first example are 60, 84 and 108, and for the second example are 45, 63 and 81 respectively. The magic rectangles of order 2×5 are of equal sums.

Result 5.16. Let's consider following *self-made algebraic pandiagonal magic square* of order 9:

$(1/5)*S$	$(2/5)*S-A11$	$A1-A9+(2/5)*S-A10$	$2*A9+A7+3*A6-A1$	$3*A9+(2/5)*S+A7-A8+3*A6-3*A1$	$(2/5)*S+A1-2*A9-A7-3*A6$	$2*A1-2*A9+A10-A7+A8-3*A6-(1/5)*S$	A11	$(1/5)*S$
A11	S/5	$3*S/5-A6-A1$	$(4/5)*S-3*A6-A1-A9$	$A8-3*A6+3*A1-3*A9-A7$	$A1+A9-(2/5)*S+3*A6$	$3*A9+A7-A8+4*A6-2*A1$	S/5	$(2/5)*S-A11$
$A9+A10-(1/5)*S$	A6	A1	A2	$3*A9-A3+(4/5)*S+A7-A2-A8+3*A6-3*A1$	A3	$(1/5)*S-A7+A8-3*A6+2*A1-3*A9$	$2*S/5-A6$	$(3/5)*S-A9-A10$
$(2/5)*S-A8$	$A8+2*A1-A9-(2/5)*S-A7$	$(3/5)*S-2*A1+2*A9+A7-A8+3*A6-A2$	A4	$A3-A7+A2+A8-3*A6+3*A1-A4-A5-3*A9$	A5	$(2/5)*S-A3-A1+A9$	$A7-2*A1+A9+(4/5)*S-A8$	A8
$(2/5)*S-A9$	A9	$A3-A7+A2+A8-3*A6+2*A1-A4-3*A9$	$(2/5)*S-A2-A3-A1+A9+A5$	$(1/5)*S$	$(3/5)*S-2*A1+2*A9+A7-A8+3*A6-A2-A3+A4$	$A1+A2+A3-A5-S/5$	$(2/5)*S-A9$	A9
A8	$A7-2*A1+A9+(4/5)*S-A8$	$S/5-A3+A4$	$2*A9+(2/5)*S+A7-A8+3*A6-A5-A1$	$A2+A3-S/5$	$(2/5)*S-A4+A1-2*A9-A7+A8-3*A6$	$S/5-A2+A5$	$A8+2*A1-A9-(2/5)*S-A7$	$(2/5)*S-A8$
$(2/5)*S-A10$	$(3/5)*S-A6-A9$	$(1/5)*S-A1+A9$	$A3+2*A1-3*A9+(1/5)*S-A7+A8-3*A6-A4$	$S/5-A2-A3+A4+A5$	$A1+A2-A5$	$2*A9+(2/5)*S+A7-A8+3*A6-2*A1$	$A9+A6-(1/5)*S$	A10
$(2/5)*S-A11$	S/5	$A6+A1-S/5$	$A1+A9-(2/5)*S+3*A6$	$3*A9+(2/5)*S+A7-A8+3*A6-3*A1$	$(4/5)*S-3*A6-A1-A9$	$(2/5)*S-A7+A8-4*A6+2*A1-3*A9$	S/5	A11
$(1/5)*S$	A11	$A9+A10-A1$	$(2/5)*S+A1-2*A9-A7-3*A6$	$A8+3*A1-A7-3*A6-3*A9$	$2*A9+A7+3*A6-A1$	$(3/5)*S-2*A1+2*A9-A10+A7-A8+3*A6$	$(2/5)*S-A11$	S/5

• Details

It is a *single-digit bordered pandiagonal magic square* of order 9 embedded with a *pandiagonal magic square* of orders 7 and 5. The magic sum of orders 7 and 9 are given as $T_{7 \times 7} = \frac{7}{5} \times S$, and $T_{9 \times 9} = \frac{9}{5} \times S$, where S is the magic sum of order 5. The magic squares of orders 5, 7 and 9 are *pandiagonal*. See below two examples:

Example 5.16. Let's consider following two examples of *pandiagonal magic squares* of order 9 based on the Result 5.16:

9x9	pan	54	54	54	54	54	54	54	54	54	9x9	pan	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81
54	6	-28	-49	161	156	-149	-89	40	6	54	81	9	-22	-43	161	162	-143	-92	40	9	81
54	40	6	-17	-95	-144	107	179	6	-28	54	81	40	9	-8	-83	-144	101	179	9	-22	81
54	65	25	10	13	139	16	-148	-13	-53	54	81	62	25	10	13	151	16	-145	-7	-44	81
54	-19	-23	125	19	-156	22	20	35	31	54	81	-13	-29	134	19	-156	22	26	47	31	81
54	-22	34	-144	29	6	128	11	-22	34	54	81	-16	34	-144	35	9	137	8	-16	34	81
54	31	35	9	120	23	-137	15	-23	-19	54	81	31	47	12	126	20	-131	18	-29	-13	81
54	-25	-41	30	-151	18	1	132	53	37	54	81	-19	-32	33	-148	21	1	138	50	37	81
54	-28	6	29	107	156	-95	-167	6	40	54	81	-22	9	26	101	162	-83	-161	9	40	81
	6	40	61	-149	-144	161	101	-28	6	54		9	40	61	-143	-144	161	110	-22	9	81
©IJT	54	54	54	54	54	54	54	54	54	54	©IJT	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81

The magic sums of magic squares of orders 5, 7 and 9 for the first example are 30, 42 and 54, and for the second example are 45, 63 and 81 respectively.

Result 5.17. Let's consider following *self-made algebraic pandiagonal magic square* of order 9:

$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$	$(-A4)$	$(2/3)*M-A3$	M	$A3$	$A4$	$M/3$	$M/3$
$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$	M	$(2/3)*M-A2$	$(-1/3)*M$	$A2$	$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$	$M/3$
$(2/3)*M+A4$	$(-1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$	$A1$	$2*M/3-A1$	M	$2*M/3-M$	M	$(-A4)$
$A3$	$A2$	$(2/3)*M-A1$	$M/3$	$A1$	$M/3$	$M/3$	$(2/3)*M-A2$	$((2/3)*M-A3)$
$(-1/3)*M$	M	$A1$	$(2/3)*M-A1$	$(1/3)*M$	$(-A1)$	$(2/3)*M+A1$	$(-1/3)*M$	M
$(2/3)*M-A3$	$(2/3)*M-A2$	$(-1/3)*M$	$M/3$	$M+A1-M/3$	$(1/3)*M$	$(2/3)*M-A1$	$A2$	$A3$
$(2/3)*M-A4$	$(1/3)*M$	M	$M/3$	$(-A1)$	$A1$	$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$	$A4$
$(2/3)*M-M/3$	$(1/3)*M$	$(-1/3)*M$	$A2$	M	$(2/3)*M-A2$	$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$	$M/3$
$(2/3)*M-M/3$	$(1/3)*M$	$(2/3)*M+A4$	$A3$	$(-1/3)*M$	$(2/3)*M-A3$	$(2/3)*M-A4$	$(2/3)*M-M/3$	$(1/3)*M$

• Details

It is a *single-digit bordered pandiagonal magic square* of order 9 embedded with a *pandiagonal magic square* of orders 7. It contains *cornered pandiagonal magic square* of order 5 having magic square of order 5 at the upper-left corner. The magic sum of orders 5, 7 and 9 are given as $T_{5 \times 5} = \frac{5}{3} \times M$, $T_{7 \times 7} = \frac{7}{3} \times S$, and $T_{9 \times 9} = 3 \times M$, where M is the magic sum of order 3. The magic squares of orders 5, 7 and 9 are *pandiagonal*. See below two examples:

Example 5.17. Let's consider following two examples of *pandiagonal magic squares* of order 9 based on the Result 5.17:

9x9	pan	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	9x9	pan	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81
108	12	12	-19	8	36	16	19	12	12	108	81	9	9	-19	2	27	16	19	9	9	81
108	12	12	36	11	-12	13	12	12	12	108	81	9	9	27	5	-9	13	9	9	9	81
108	43	-12	12	10	14	36	-12	36	-19	108	81	37	-9	9	10	8	27	-9	27	-19	81
108	16	13	14	12	10	12	12	11	8	108	81	16	13	8	9	10	9	9	5	2	81
108	-12	36	10	14	12	-10	34	-12	36	108	81	-9	27	10	8	9	-10	28	-9	27	81
108	8	11	-12	12	34	12	14	13	16	108	81	2	5	-9	9	28	9	8	13	16	81
108	5	12	36	12	-10	10	12	12	19	108	81	-1	9	27	9	-10	10	9	9	19	81
108	12	12	-12	13	36	11	12	12	12	108	81	9	9	-9	13	27	5	9	9	9	81
	12	12	43	16	-12	8	5	12	12	108		9	9	37	16	-9	2	-1	9	9	81
©IJT	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	©IJT	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81

The magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9 for the first example are 36, 60, 84 and 108 and for the second example are 27, 45, 63 and 81 respectively.

Result 5.18. Let's consider following *self-made algebraic pandiagonal magic square* of order 9:

$(1/3)*M$	$(2/3)*M-A6$	$(1/3)*M+A2-A5$	$(2/3)*M-A4$	$(2/3)*M-A2$	A4	A5	A6	$(1/3)*M$
A6	M/3	$(2/3)*M-A3$	$A2+(1/3)*M-3*A3$	A2	$3*A3+(1/3)*M-A2$	$M/3+A3-A2$	M/3	$(2/3)*M-A6$
$(1/3)*M-A2+A5$	A3	M/3	$A1-A2+M/3$	M/3	$M-A1-M/3$	A2	$(2/3)*M-A3$	$(1/3)*M+A2-A5$
A4	$3*A3+(1/3)*M-A2$	$(1/3)*M+A2-A1$	$2*M/3-M/3$	$M/3+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$A1-A2+M/3$	$A2+(1/3)*M-3*A3$	$(2/3)*M-A4$
A2	$(2/3)*M-A2$	M/3	$(2/3)*M-A2$	M/3	A2	M/3	A2	$(2/3)*M-A2$
$(2/3)*M-A4$	$A2+(1/3)*M-$	A1	A2	$M-M/3-A2$	M/3	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*A3+(1/3)*M-A2$	A4
$(2/3)*M-A5$	$(1/3)*M-A3+A2$	$2*M/3-A2$	$M/3+A2-A1$	M/3	$M/3+A1-M/3$	$(1/3)*M$	$A3+M/3-A2$	A5
$(2/3)*M-A6$	$(2/3)*M-M/3$	A3	$3*A3+(1/3)*M-A2$	$(2/3)*M-A2$	$A2+(1/3)*M-$	$(1/3)*M-A3+A2$	$(1/3)*M$	A6
$(1/3)*M$	A6	$(1/3)*M-A2+A5$	A4	A2	$(2/3)*M-A4$	$(2/3)*M-A5$	$(2/3)*M-A6$	M/3

• Details

It is a *single-digit bordered pandiagonal magic square* of order 9 embedded with *pandiagonal magic squares* of orders 5 and 7. The magic square of order 3 is in the inner part. The magic sum of orders 5, 7 and 9 are given as $T_{5 \times 5} = \frac{5}{3} \times M$, $T_{7 \times 7} = \frac{7}{3} \times S$, and $T_{9 \times 9} = 3 \times M$, where M is the magic sum of order 3. The magic squares of orders 5, 7 and 9 are *pandiagonal*. See below two examples:

Example 5.18. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 9 based on the Result ??:

9x9	pan	72	72	72	72	72	72	72	72	72	9x9	pan	63	63	63	63	63	63	63	63	63
72	8	0	5	2	4	14	15	16	8	72	63	7	-2	4	0	2	14	15	16	7	63
72	16	8	3	-19	12	35	9	8	0	72	63	16	7	1	-20	12	34	8	7	-2	63
72	11	13	8	7	8	5	12	3	5	72	63	10	13	7	6	7	3	12	1	4	63
72	14	35	9	8	12	4	7	-19	2	72	63	14	34	8	7	12	2	6	-20	0	63
72	12	4	8	4	8	12	8	12	4	72	63	12	2	7	2	7	12	7	12	2	63
72	2	-19	11	12	4	8	5	35	14	72	63	0	-20	11	12	2	7	3	34	14	63
72	1	7	4	9	8	11	8	9	15	72	63	-1	6	2	8	7	11	7	8	15	63
72	0	8	13	35	4	-19	7	8	16	72	63	-2	7	13	34	2	-20	6	7	16	63
	8	16	11	14	12	2	1	0	8	72		7	16	10	14	12	0	-1	-2	7	63
©IJT	72	72	72	72	72	72	72	72	72	72	©IJT	63	63	63	63	63	63	63	63	63	63

The magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9 for the first example are 24, 40 56 and 72 and for the second example are 21, 35, 49 and 63 respectively.

6 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares,

(i) <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=668>

(ii) <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers,

(i) <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=671>

(ii) <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

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